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Master's Degree Final Project

**Development and Implementation of a C++
Inverse Kinematics Library for Highly Redundant Robots**

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Abstract

The main objective of the following project is the development of an efficient kinematics library for highly redundant robots. It is focused on the inverse kinematics problem and redundancy resolution of a 11 degree of freedom robot for the Future Circular Collider. The entirety of this thesis is developed at CERN and it is implemented in C++ adapting within the CERN Robotic Framework (CRF). The library is written in a modular and generic way, such that it can be used for the entire robotic fleet at CERN. First of all, this report describes the main methods used nowadays to solve the inverse kinematics problem and explains why the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) algorithm, based on the Jacobian, is chosen for the given robotic system. The next step is the implementation of the CLIK algorithm following a modular structure in order to enable future users to easily extend the library. For this, the main code of the algorithm, and other complementary programs that are called by it, have been written, forming a kinematics library. Finally, the report exposes the results of the algorithm tests performed in simulation as well as on a real system using a Universal Robot UR10e.

Keywords: Robotics, Inverse Kinematics, CLIK, Redundant manipulator

UNESCO codes: 3311.01, 3311.02, 3399 (Robotics)

Resumen

El objetivo principal de este proyecto es el desarrollo de una librería de cinemática eficiente para robots hiper-redundantes. Se centra en el problema de cinemática inversa y la resolución de la redundancia de un robot de 11 grados de libertad para el Future Circular Collider. Todo el TFM está desarrollado en el CERN y está implementado en C++ adaptándose al entorno del CERN Robotic Framework (CRF). La librería está escrita de forma modular y genérica, de modo que pueda utilizarse para toda la flota robótica del CERN. En primer lugar, este informe describe los principales métodos utilizados hoy en día para resolver el problema de cinemática inversa y explica por qué se elige el algoritmo de cinemática inversa de lazo cerrado (CLIK), basado en el jacobiano, para el sistema robótico dado. El siguiente paso es la implementación del algoritmo CLIK siguiendo una estructura modular para permitir a los futuros usuarios ampliar fácilmente la biblioteca. Para ello, se ha escrito el código principal del algoritmo, y otros programas complementarios que son llamados por el mismo, formando una librería cinemática. Finalmente, el informe expone los resultados de las pruebas de algoritmos realizadas tanto en simulación como en un sistema real utilizando un robot UR10e de Universal Robots.

Palabras clave: Robótica, Cinemática Inversa, CLIK, Manipulador Redundante

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1. INTRODUCTION

Standard industrial robotic arms usually come with a software interface developed at the robot company. These software frameworks facilitate the user with functionality like low-level control of the motors, sensor reading, high-level controls like impedance control of the complete mechanical structure or inverse kinematic solutions for the specific topology and geometry of the acquired robot.

Thanks to these functionalities the movement of each of its joints or the motion of the end-effector can be controlled in a user-friendly way.

The user interface of one software example can be seen at Fig. 1. This is the case of the Universal Robots (UR) Graphical Programming Environment. Both types of control mentioned before can be observed. The controls of the end-effector position are squared in orange and the joint position controls are squared in purple.

Fig. 1. Universal Robots Graphical Programming Environment with UR10e robot.

However, the robotic section at CERN (European Council for Nuclear Research), the organisation in which this work has been carried out, is often challenged with very specific tasks that lead to very specific requirements for their robotic solutions in terms of payload, robot weight, dexterity, topology and workspace.

Standard industrial robots often do not satisfy these requirements, which forces the development of customized robotic solutions and as a consequence, the development customized of software solutions.

A recent project at CERN required the development and control of a highly redundant robotic arm, including the mechanical design as well as the control algorithms and software. A key challenge for highly redundant robots is the inverse kinematics problem for which the CERN Robotic Framework (CRF), which is a compilation of programs written by the section workers since 2017, didn't offer satisfying solutions at the time this thesis was started. Thus, this Master's Degree Final Project (MDFP) focused on the development and implementation of a modular inverse kinematics library for the CRF in C++.

Nowadays there are many methods to solve inverse kinematics (IK) problem. With geometric and analytic techniques, closed form solutions can be obtained. For complex cases, only numerical solutions can be obtained using Heuristic, Newton, and Jacobian based techniques, among many others. Furthermore, several of these methods have already been implemented in libraries with different programming languages.

In this project, the programming of the technique known as Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) is carried out, using the C++ programming language. The method and the programming language utilized, between other decisions, have been made based on the requirements demanded by the CERN.

The CERN laboratory [1] was founded in 1954 and it is situated at both sides of the Franco-Swiss border near Geneva. Its main area of research is particle physics. Engineers at CERN develop and use scientific instruments to accelerate subatomic particles close to the speed of light and force them into collisions, such that physicists can study the basic constituents of matter and draw conclusions about the particles interaction and the fundamental laws of nature. The world's largest and most powerful particle accelerator is the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), made of a 27 km ring of superconducting magnets with a number of accelerating structures to boost the energy of the particles along the way.

Around 2040, once the LHC high luminosity phase (HL-LHC) reaches its conclusion, to extend the research currently being carried out at the LHC, a new research infrastructure will need to be built to host the next generation of higher performance particle colliders. This is the objective of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) study (Fig. 2). As CERN explains in [2], the goal of the FCC is to push the energy and intensity frontiers of particle colliders, with the aim of reaching collision energies of 100 TeV in a new 80-100 km circumference tunnel, in the search for new physics.

Fig. 2. Schematic map showing a possible location for the Future Circular Collider [2].

More than 150 universities, research institutes and industrial partners from all over the world are collaborating to develop different possibilities for circular colliders, new detector facilities, the associated infrastructure, operation concepts and key technologies required, as well as cost estimates, global implementation scenarios, and the appropriate international governance structures.

One of these projects is the development of the FCC robotic system and the conclusion of part of the research is that the optimal robotic solutions, that fulfils all requirements, consists of a 10 degrees of freedom (DOF) robotic arm mounted on rails that allow the robotic arm to travel along the tunnel axis and lead to a total of 11 DOF. It can be observed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Simulation of the FCC robot prototype.

A reason for using robots at CERN facilities is the presence of radiation related to the particle experiments. In these environments the human presence is restricted in order to protect the workers' health. Performing maintenance and inspection tasks in these hazardous environments is one of the main use cases for the robotic fleet at CERN.

Although the main objective of this MDFP is the development and implementation of the IK solution to be used for the FCC robot, it is not exclusive, it is done in a generic way so that it can solve the kinematics of any robot.

Like this project is carried out within the CERN, the implementation must be adapted and must be coupled within the existing framework in the section, the CERN Robotic Framework. The majority of the programs are written in C++, but there also are some in Python. So, the methodology taken to implement the programs done for this project follow the CRF structure.

As the 11 DOF robot has not yet been built during the realization of this project, the programs are tested with the UR10e 6 DOF robot, which corresponds to the last 6 DOF of the FCC robot, getting good results.

1.1. Objectives

The main objective of this Master's Degree Final Project is the resolution of the inverse kinematics problem for carrying out the control in position of a redundant robot, with 11 degrees of freedom, avoiding singularities.

The program needs to be inserted in the existing C++ CERN Robotic Framework (CRF), so it must be written in C++ language and to be compatible to the rest of the existing codes that belongs to the CRF. If necessary, existing programs can be changed but without negatively impacting any others that are using them.

The work carried out must be completed with the documentation and prepared for the subsequent extension of the project that will consist of adding Objective Functions to set some restrictions to the robot. It also should be open to future new implementations of other kinematic solutions.

Although the main objective of this MDFP is the development and implementation of the IK solution to be used in the FCC robot, it is not exclusive, it is done in a generic way so that it can solve the kinematics of any robot.

2. STATE OF THE ART

The term robot appeared for first time to refer the automaton build by Rossum in the play Rossum's Universal Robots (R.U.R.) written by the Czech Karel Capek in 1920. This term is based in the word *robota* whose meaning is forced labour in Slav languages [3].

The science fiction writer Isaac Asimov was who clearly defined the robot as a mechanical artifact in his books introducing the "three fundamental laws:

1. A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm.
2. A robot must obey the orders given it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the First Law.
3. A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Law."

During years the word robot has been associated to science fiction, but over the years, it has become part of the real technology.

The definition of the term robot was and is still difficult due to the high mix of concepts between the reality and the fiction.

The first trials of create a standard technical definition [4] were done in 1979 by the then Robot Institute of America (RIA), the current Robotic Industries Association. In this "A robot is a reprogrammable, multifunctional manipulator designed to move material, parts, tools or specialized devices through variable programmed motions for the performance of a variety of tasks".

This definition has been the base for future definitions, including the current one presented by the International Standard Organization (ISO), written in the norm ISO 8373 [5]: "An industrial robot is an automatically controlled, reprogrammable, multipurpose manipulator, programmable in three or more axes which may be either fixed in place or mobile for use in industrial automation applications".

Depending on its mechanical structure, robots can be classified in two main groups: mobile robots, those with a mobile base, and manipulator robots, those with a fixed base [3].

The fundamental feature of mobile robots is the mobile base component which allows the robot to move freely. From a mechanical point of view, mobile robots consist of one or several rigid bodies equipped with a locomotion system, like wheels or legs, as can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Mobile robots classification. (a) Wheeled. (b) Legged (Based on [6]).

The mechanical structure of a manipulator robot is a sequence of rigid bodies, links, interconnected through articulations, joints. The articulation between two successive links can be executed by means of a prismatic or a revolute joint. A revolute joint creates a relative rotational motion between the two links, whereas a prismatic joint creates a relative

translational motion between the two links. Each of these both joints provide the structure with a single DOF when the structure is an open kinematic chain, meaning there is only one sequence of links connecting the two ends of the chain. In order to have sufficient degrees of freedom to execute a given task, these should be correctly distributed along the mechanical structure. A manipulator robot is made up of an arm that assure manoeuvrability, a wrist that grants dexterity and an end-effector that carries out the task entrusted to the robot. Six DOF are demanded in a three-dimensional space, three for positioning and three for orienting the end-effector. If more DOFs than task variables are available, from a kinematic point of view, the manipulator is called redundant robot. The type and disposition from the base joint to the end-effector of the arm's DOFs gives rise to a classification of manipulators (Fig. 5) as cartesian, cylindrical, SCARA, spherical, and anthropomorphic.

Fig. 5. Manipulator robots classification by the type and sequence of the arm's DOF [4].
 (a) Cartesian. (b) Cylindrical. (c) SCARA. (d) Spherical. (e) Anthropomorphic.

A robot can be also the combination of both, merging the structure of a manipulator with a locomotion system. In the Fig. 6 there is an example of mobile manipulator robot which combines the unlimited mobility of the base with the dexterity of the articulated arm.

Fig. 6. Mobile manipulator robot (Based on [3]).

In order to control the performance of the manipulator robot, it is necessary to define the end-effector position and orientation motion in the task space, and therefore the resulting movement of the whole structure, from the base to the end-effector, that is composed of the elementary action of each link respecting the previous one.

The study of the movement of robots with respect to a reference system is what is known as kinematics. It does not consider the forces that may intervene. Kinematics describes analytically the motion as function of time, relating the end-effector position and orientation with the joint coordinates.

2.1. Inverse kinematics

As it can be seen in Fig. 7, kinematics has two fundamental problems to resolve that relates the joint space with the task space, also known as cartesian or operational space.

Fig. 7. Robot Kinematics.

The first problem is called forward kinematics (FK) and determine the position and orientation (pose), \mathbf{s} , of the end-effector knowing the characteristics of the robot and the position θ of its joints, $\mathbf{q} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n]^T$, being n the number of joints.

$$\mathbf{s} = f(\mathbf{q}) \quad (1)$$

The second is known as inverse kinematics (IK) and consists in finding the joints' configuration that the robot should have to get the known desired end-effector position and orientation, \mathbf{s}_d .

$$\mathbf{q} = f^{-1}(\mathbf{s}_d) \quad (2)$$

The inverse kinematics problem for serial robotic arms is more complex than forward kinematics due to the following reasons [3]:

- There may be no acceptable solutions in case the given end-effector pose doesn't belong to the workspace of the robot, that is, the target is further away than the chain can reach, or it is a point that the chain cannot get to with any combination of turns [7].
- Also, multiple solutions may exist, infinite in case of a kinematically redundant manipulator.
- The procedure to find a closed-form solution is strongly dependent from the robot configuration and achieving the closed-form solution is not always possible due to the generally nonlinear equations. In these cases, the use of numerical solution techniques might be appropriate, as they are applicable to any kinematic structure, but considering that usually they don't compute all admissible solutions.

2. STATE OF THE ART

In applications when the inverse kinematics need to be solved in real time [4] is very useful having a close-form solution, since numerical solution techniques might not find a solution in the needed time. Also, close-form is useful to define restrictions for choosing the most adequate solution in the cases it is not unique.

Analytic/geometric method can be used for obtaining the close-form solution (2). It consists of finding an enough number of algebraic relations between the coordinates of the end-effector of the robot, its joint coordinates and the physical dimensions of its links. Using the Gröbner Bases theory, the set of equations can be transformed to a standard equivalent form which is simpler to solve. According to [8], “the analytical IK solutions usually do not suffer from singularity problems, they offer a global solution, and they are reliable, which is the main reason why they are exploited in robotics”. Although these methods are used to obtain closed solutions, they are not guaranteed [9].

The previous method usually is used for the 3 first links that normally set the position coordinates of the end-effector although it also can be used for the rest of the links adding more complexity.

Generally, setting a specific orientation with the wrist is also needed. If the axis of the wrist intersects at one point, the technique called Kinematic Decoupling may be used. Taking profit of this fact, position and orientation problems can be separated, establishing the coordinates of the wrist intersection point for calculating the previous joints coordinates. And later, taking the already calculated joints positions and the desired end-effector orientation, the wrist joint positions can be calculated.

As it mentioned above, in the complex cases of the IK problem or for generic ones is more convenient work with methods to obtain numerical solutions. These include, between others, the techniques that require a set of iterations to achieve a satisfactory solution. The iterative methods formulate the problem using a cost function to be minimized [8]. There are three main families to obtain numerical solutions: Heuristic, Newton based, and Jacobian based. There are also other known techniques as Learnt and Deep Learning methods or Statistics methods, etc.

2.1.1. Heuristics methods

The heuristic techniques are really useful when there is no information about the robotic system, and one of the main benefits is the speediness because they have less computational cost than other methods, like Jacobian based. Normally, these algorithms are composed of simple operations that get the IK solution gradually in an iterative manner and are really good for non-complex problems. Cyclic Coordinate Descent (CCD), Triangulation and Forward and backward reaching inverse kinematics (FABRIK) are some of the most used heuristic methods [8].

- Cyclic Coordinate Descent

It is a very popular IK method, according to [7]. Examples of its use are the computer game industry, the protein structure prediction and robotics. As it is explained in [7] and [8], the CCD method try to minimise the end-effector pose error by moving the joint positions one by one, beginning from the end-effector and continuing to the manipulator base, and repeating the process until a satisfactory solution is obtained. Like other techniques, for a desired end-effector pose CCD can generate many different joint configurations, resulting really difficult to choose a feasible one, so constraints must be incorporated.

Cyclic Coordinate Descent is a heuristic iterative method easy to implement, that can solve the IK problem without matrix manipulations which makes it has an extremely low computational cost for each joint per iteration and it formulates a solution very quickly. Local constraints are also easy to apply too. Nevertheless, CCD produces motion with erratic discontinuities due to the generation of big angle rotations, and also it is prone to overemphasise the movements of the joints nearer to the end-effector, even if manipulator restrictions have been indicated, especially in highly articulated ones, because global manipulation constraints are difficult to implement. Furthermore, in case of requiring high accuracy, for specific target positions the algorithm can spend a huge number of iterations, resulting in noisy motion of the end-effector.

- Triangulation IK

This method does not use an iterative approach. It utilizes the cosine rule to compute each joint angle, beginning from the robot base until the last link. When the target is inside the workspace, the solution is guaranteed if there are not constraints in the joints since each joint is calculated independently without include the restrictions of the following joint.

Like the algorithm only needs one iteration, the Triangulation algorithm is less computationally costly than CCD, so is faster. However, the results are not feasible, since the joints near the end-effector are normally in a straight line, leaving all the rotation to the joints close to the base.

- Forward and backward reaching inverse kinematics

It functions in a forward and backward iterative fashion, minimizing one at a time the distance between the target and the end-effector. Starting from the last joint of the manipulator, the algorithm utilizes the earlier computed positions of the joints to find the updates to adjust each joint until the base. Afterwards, it works towards the back in the same way, for the purpose of complete a full iteration. This routine is repeated all the needed times until the solution is equal or sufficient close to the target. When the desired pose is reachable, FABRIK converges to it on all occasions unless there are constraints that prevent the robot to bend enough.

As this method obtains the joints configuration solving the problem in an equivalent way to solve the problem of finding a point on a line instead of applying angle rotations, the computational cost is low, and also easy to implement. Other advantages are their good balance near the singularities, the return of a smooth motion without erratic discontinuities, and the smooth angle distribution between all the joints. This last advantage differs from CCD, which emphasizes the movement next to the end-effector. On the other hand, it is necessary consider that FABRIK resolve the inverse kinematics in position space, dealing with the orientations in a different step, what adds complexity and causes less continuity under orientation restrictions. Furthermore, as CCD, this method is not capable to implement global constraints that meet the spatio-temporal correlations between close joints.

2.1.2. Newton based methods

As expounded in [7] and [8], the Newton based methods are based on a second order Taylor series expansion of the object function:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \approx \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + [\nabla \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})]^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{x}) \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (3)$$

where $f(x + \sigma)$ are the desired joint parameters, $f(x)$ are the current joint parameters, σ is the modification so that $f(x)$ requires for satisfying $f(x + \sigma)$ and $H_f(x)$ is the Hessian matrix.

They return smooth motion without erratic discontinuities since they solve minimization problems in order to seek target configurations. The integration of joint restrictions is also easy, and thanks to the Newton approach, the singularity problems are avoided. The bad side is that these techniques are complex, what it entails difficulty in the implementation and a big computational cost per iteration.

The most renowned techniques are Broyden's method, Powell's method, Siciliano's method, and the Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb and Shanno (BFGS) method.

2.1.3. Jacobian based methods

One of the most popular numerical strategies is the linear approximation to the IK problem using the Jacobian, $J(q)$ [7] [8]. It is the relation between the joints velocity, $\dot{q} = [\dot{\theta}_1, \dots, \dot{\theta}_n]^T$, and the corresponding end-effector linear and angular velocity, \dot{s} . Thus, $J(q)$ is a $k \times n$ matrix, where k is the number of the task space dimensions and n is the number of joints.

$$\dot{s} = J(q) \cdot \dot{q} \quad (4)$$

There are two main processes to obtain the Jacobian. Computing the partial derivatives of the entire chain system relative to the end effector, that is, the direct kinematics function with respect to the joints, for getting the analytical Jacobian. Otherwise, getting the relationship between the joints velocity and the corresponding end-effector linear and angular velocity in a matrix called geometric Jacobian. It is necessary to remark that, unlike the analytical Jacobian, the geometric one does not contain representation singularities.

Knowing that the FK problem can be expressed as (4), the IK problem can be rewritten as

$$\dot{q} = J(q)^{-1} \cdot \dot{s} \quad (5)$$

where $J(q)^{-1}$ is the inverse Jacobian.

Jacobian inverse kinematics approach produces smooth postures. However, in most cases, the IK equation cannot be solved uniquely. Indeed, the Jacobian J may not be square or invertible, and even if it is invertible, solving J means high computational cost and complex matrix calculations. Even it may work poorly as it may be nearly singular.

Aiming to avoid singularity problems and improve the convergence and the stability of the solution, several different approximation methods have been proposed to solve the IK problem. The main ones are exposed below:

- Jacobian transposed

This approximation uses the transposed Jacobian instead of its inverse, multiplied by a factor. Due to the non-linear forward kinematic model, the factor should be positive and small enough to avoid the appearance of oscillations and discontinuities.

This method has less computation cost, but the results differ specially in cases when the difference between one pose and the following one is significant.

- Jacobian pseudo-inverse

It is also known as the Moore-Penrouse inverse of the Jacobian. It can be expressed as

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger \cdot \dot{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger (\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^\dagger)^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{s}} \quad (6)$$

being \mathbf{J}^\dagger the pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{J} .

Analysing the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [10], the Jacobian can be expressed as the $m \times n$ matrix

$$\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}^\mathbf{T} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{U} is an $m \times m$ unitary orthogonal matrix, \mathbf{D} is an $m \times n$ rectangular diagonal matrix with nonnegative real numbers on the diagonal σ , and $\mathbf{V}^\mathbf{T}$ is another unitary orthogonal matrix. Thus, the pseudo-inverse Jacobian using SVD can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{J}^\dagger = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{D}^\dagger\mathbf{U}^\mathbf{T} = \sum \sigma^{-1} \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}^\mathbf{T} \quad (8)$$

being \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} each column of the \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} matrices respectively.

The main benefit of the pseudo-inverse is that it can be obtained even for non-squared Jacobian, \mathbf{J} . Furthermore, it can help to avoid singular configuration using the null space method, since the matrix $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{J}^\dagger \mathbf{J})$ represents the orthogonal projection matrix into the null space of \mathbf{J} . The null space is useful for changing the joints configuration without moving the end-effector. However, close to singularities this method obtains large differences at joint angles from small changes in the target, resulting in discontinuities and oscillations.

- Damped Least Squares (DLS) pseudo-inverse

DLS pseudo-inverse, also known as Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm is another variation of the Jacobian. DLS pseudo-inverse avoids many of the singularity problems of the pseudo-inverse approach, giving a result more stable. It is computed as

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\mathbf{T} (\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^\mathbf{T} + \alpha \mathbf{I})^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{s}} \quad (9)$$

where α is a non-zero damping factor. The damping constant must be a real number chosen to make (9) numerically stable.

The behaviour of DLS pseudo-inverse is better than the two previous Jacobian methods, but it depends on α . The solutions near singularities are better as large is the damping factor. However, α should be chosen carefully because with the increment of α , the convergence rate and the accuracy decrease, and more oscillations are caused.

From the point of view of SVD the DLS pseudo-inverse technique can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{J}^\mathbf{T} (\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^\mathbf{T} + \alpha \mathbf{I})^{-1} = \sum \frac{\sigma}{\sigma^2 + \alpha} \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}^\mathbf{T} \quad (10)$$

Far from singularities, the simple pseudo-inverse and pseudo-inverse DLS techniques perform similarly. The difference appears in areas near singularities. Simple pseudo-inverse case becomes unstable when σ approaches zero, while pseudo-inverse DLS method acts smoothly.

- Selectively Damped Least Squares (SDLS)

This is an extension of the previous Jacobian method. Depending on the difficulty to reach the desired pose, SDLS adjusts the damping factor separately for each singular vector of the Jacobian SVD.

The DLS and pseudo-inverse DLS Jacobian approaches are computationally cheaper and easier to implement than the SDLS technique. However, SDLS gives improved performance avoiding oscillations for applications where it is difficult to choose a good damping factor and where runtime is not restricted.

- Incorporating constraints

The incorporation of restrictions increases the utility of the IK solution in some applications. With Jacobian family methods, this process has some difficulties, and the optimal solution is not guaranteed. Nevertheless, a lot of methods have been developed computing and applying penalties and a weight matrix for limiting the joints movements, avoiding collisions, setting desired joints positions and avoiding singularities between others.

2.1.4. Other methods

Other techniques are also being used to solve IK problem [8], as

- Learnt and Deep Learning methods

The idea of these techniques is to use previously learnt configurations to match the pose of the end-effector to a feasible pose learnt from the database.

There are two main groups of Learnt methods: error-based, which improve the inverse kinematic estimation used to reach the desired position, and example-based, which use example postures to learn the inverse kinematic estimation.

Instead of looking for the closest posture that matches the constraints, Deep Learning methods use neural networks to learn the articulated movement through optimization processes from real movements. In other words, they are used to learn the relations between high-level control parameters and low-level joint translations and rotations.

- Statistic methods

Hybrid techniques comprise another family of methods that solve the IK problem. In an attempt to reduce the complexity of the optimization problem, they decompose the IK problem into analytical and numerical components.

An example of this kind of methods is the Sequential Monte Carlo methods (SMCM) [7]. It is a statistical method that uses a sampling approach for solving the IK problem with FK, thus avoiding the computation of the inverse matrix.

2.2. Inverse kinematics libraries

There are some libraries in the market that offer functions for computing inverse kinematics.

- Kinematic and Dynamic Library (KDL)

This C++ library is an Open Robot Control Software (Orocos) [11] project that can be used independently. It has been created to supply real time and safe usable kinematics and dynamics code, as it is explained in [12].

It can be used for 3D frames, vector and points transformations, for modelling kinematic chains and access their kinematic and dynamic properties, such as forward and inverse kinematics and dynamics of robots, biomechanical human models, machine tools, etc., and to specify motion trajectories of frames and kinematic chains of various families (serial, humanoid, parallel, mobile, ...), such as trapezoidal velocity profiles.

- Pinocchio

Pinocchio [13] is an open-source, mostly written in C++ library for efficiently computing the dynamics of a robot model and their analytical derivatives. This library does not only include standard algorithms employed in robotics (like the Recursive Newton-Euler Algorithm or the Articulated-Body Algorithm) but provides additional features essential for the control, the planning and the simulation of robots. Pinocchio is one of the most efficient libraries for computing the dynamics of articulated bodies.

- CasADI-Based Closed-Loop Inverse Kinematics (CASCLIK)

As it is explained in [14], CASCLIK is a python free library for rapid prototyping of constraint-based, task-priority closed-loop inverse kinematics. The module allows for combining multiple tasks that are resolved with a quadratic, nonlinear, or model predictive optimization-based approach, or a set-based task-priority inverse kinematics approach. It is a prototyping library for comparing overall strategies, and although capable of running quite fast, is not the best solution for Real-Time or finalized industrial applications.

3. THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHOSEN IK METHOD

The technique selected for solving the IK problem in this project is the Jacobian one that allows the conversion from the end-effector linear and angular velocities to the joints velocities (5).

Other methods are much faster, obtaining the solution in a local minimum. This is really useful in computer games, for situations with many end-effectors, like the generation of bodies movement. But the majority of the other methods don't use knowledge of the model and they obtain the result without giving the control of the joints configuration chosen.

Thanks to the knowledge of the model, Jacobian based methods offer the control over the joints configuration needed in this project. Furthermore, Jacobian allows the addition of restrictions, respecting the objective of leaving the project open to future additions in this field.

Since the main use of the IK in this project is being applied in the FCC robot, a redundant robot with a non-squared Jacobian matrix whose size is 11 x 6 (11 DOF and 6 components at the end-effector velocity), the inverse of the Jacobian cannot be computed. For this reason, it is used the pseudo-inversed estimation (6).

But pseudo inverse Jacobian approximation is not enough, since one of the objectives is avoiding singularities. That is why the method used is Damped Least-Squares pseudo-inverse (9), which helps to avoid the mechanical singularities (situations when a finite velocity in task space creates an infinite velocity in joint space) with the damping factor, α .

For computing the damping factor, as it is explained at [10], "the natural choice is to adjust α as a function of some measure of distance from the singularity at the current configuration of the robot arm. Far from singular configurations feasible joint velocities are obtained; thus, the accuracy requirement prevails and low damping must be used. Close to a singularity, task velocity commands along the unfeasible directions give large joint velocities and the accuracy requirement must be relaxed; in these cases, high damping is needed".

The kinematic manipulability is the tool selected for measuring the distance from a singularity. The kinematic manipulability, ω_{kin} , [15] [16] of a robot is an index for checking how good an adjustment in workspace is possible, indicating the relative capability of the robot arm to move in different directions. It corresponds to the following formula:

$$\omega_{kin} = \sqrt{\det\{J(\mathbf{q}) J^T(\mathbf{q})\}} \quad (11)$$

where $J(\mathbf{q})$ the Jacobian matrix evaluated with the \mathbf{q} joint angles and $J^T(\mathbf{q})$ the transposed one.

Selecting a manipulability value w_0 as the limit of the singular region, and α_0 as the maximum value of the damping factor, the damping factor can be obtained in the following way,

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \alpha_0 \left(1 - \frac{\omega_{kin}}{\omega_0}\right)^2 & \omega_{kin} < \omega_0 \\ 0 & \omega_{kin} \geq \omega_0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

which provide a continuous and good shaped solution.

With pseudo-inverse damped least-squares Jacobian approximation, the joints velocity is obtained. But, in this project, the objective of the inverse kinematics solution is being able to do a joints position control.

The joints position can be obtained integrating the joints velocities. A discrete numerical approximation of the integral should fit since the implementation of the joints position control is not continuous-time process.

The typical in these cases is using Euler forward rectangular integral rule, whose interpolation is

$$\mathbf{q}_{k+1} = \mathbf{q}_k + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_k \Delta t \quad (13)$$

being \mathbf{q}_{k+1} the joints position at one step, \mathbf{q}_k and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_k$ the joints position and the joints velocity at the previous step, and Δt the time step.

Taking in account that, in the control implementation, the derivative will also be needed, and Euler forward derivative looks like

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_k = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{k+1} - \mathbf{q}_k}{\Delta t} \quad (14)$$

for obtaining the joints velocity in one step, the joints position of the following step \mathbf{q}_{k+1} is needed. This is not a big deal for non-online processes, but it is an impossible to compute for real time applications when the position in the following step is not already known.

To avoid this handicap, Euler backwards rectangular rules are used in this inverse kinematics process. And it will be used also in the implementation of the joints position control. The backwards integral and derivative respectively are

$$\mathbf{q}_{k+1} = \mathbf{q}_k + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{k+1} \Delta t \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{k+1} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{k+1} - \mathbf{q}_k}{\Delta t} \quad (16)$$

With these equations, the integral and the derivative can be computed only using elements of the same or the previous step.

As it is exposed at [10], “no matter what kind of interpolation is used, the small though unavoidable error suffered at each numerical integration step accumulates, leading to long-term drifting of the reconstructed profile from the exact joint-position profile. Another source of error affecting any integral reconstruction method is the possible uncertainty in the initial value of the joint position”.

To solve this problem, it is used an algorithm that utilise a feedback correction term. This type of algorithm is known as Closed-Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) and has the structure shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. First order CLIK structure.

3. THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHOSEN IK METHOD

For obtaining the task velocity corrected (task velocity close-loop), the first step is applying FK to the current joints position, getting the current end-effector pose. The following step is the computation of the error between the current end-effector pose and the desired end-effector pose. The last step is the calculation of the feedback correction term, multiplying the resulting error times a constant positive-definite gain matrix, K , and adding it to the desired end-effector velocity.

The process to obtain the Forward Kinematics expressions is not part of this project since they are given as a resource.

Once the current end-effector pose is acquired, it is the turn of computing the error, which is composed by 6 elements: 3 from the position error and 3 from the orientation error.

The position error, $\{error_1, error_2, error_3\}$, is easy to calculate with simple subtractions

$$error_1 = x_{desired} - x_{current} \quad (17)$$

$$error_2 = y_{desired} - y_{current} \quad (18)$$

$$error_3 = z_{desired} - z_{current} \quad (19)$$

being x the position in the X axis, y the position in the Y axis and z the position in the Z axis of the desired end-effector or of the current end-effector.

But the process to calculate the orientation error is different [3]. The procedure changes depending on the representation method: Cardan, Euler, axis-angle or quaternion.

- Cardan

Cardan represents the orientation with three angles that corresponds to the rotations around the axes X-Y-Z, also known as Yaw-Pitch-Roll.

In Cardan, the orientation error, $\{error_4, error_5, error_6\}$, is as simple as the calculation of the position error

$$error_4 = \Phi_{x_{desired}} - \Phi_{x_{current}} \quad (20)$$

$$error_5 = \Phi_{y_{desired}} - \Phi_{y_{current}} \quad (21)$$

$$error_6 = \Phi_{z_{desired}} - \Phi_{z_{current}} \quad (22)$$

being Φ_x the orientation around the X axis, Φ_y the orientation around the Y axis and Φ_z the orientation around the Z axis of the desired end-effector or of the current end-effector.

- Euler

Euler also represents the orientation with three angles that corresponds to three rotations around the axes, being the first and the third rotation around the same axis. There are several combinations. In this project Euler representation rotates around the axes Z-X-Z.

In Euler ZXZ, the procedure for computing the orientation error, $\{error_4, error_5, error_6\}$, is the same as in Cardan:

$$error_4 = \Phi_{z_{desired}} - \Phi_{z_{current}} \quad (23)$$

$$error_5 = \Phi_{x_{desired}} - \Phi_{x_{current}} \quad (24)$$

$$error_6 = \Phi_{z_{desired}} - \Phi_{z_{current}} \quad (25)$$

being ϕ_z in (23) the first orientation around the Z axis, ϕ_x the orientation around the X axis and ϕ_z in (25) the second orientation around the Z axis of the desired end-effector or of the current end-effector.

- Axis-angle

Axis-angle method represents the orientation with an axis \mathbf{r} and an angle θ . The axis is expressed as unit vector $\mathbf{r} = \{r_x, r_y, r_z\}$, and it represents the axis of rotation. θ represents the angle of rotation around the axis.

The orientation error $\mathbf{e}_o = \{error_4, error_5, error_6\}$ can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{e}_o = \mathbf{r} \sin(\theta) \quad (26)$$

where \mathbf{r} and θ are the axis and the angle of the equivalent rotation of the matrix

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{r}, \theta) = \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{R}_c^T \quad (27)$$

being $\mathbf{R}_d = [\mathbf{n}_d \ \mathbf{s}_d \ \mathbf{a}_d]$ the desired orientation expressed in the rotation matrix form and $\mathbf{R}_c = [\mathbf{n}_c \ \mathbf{s}_c \ \mathbf{a}_c]$ the current rotation matrix.

Then, the solution of the orientation error is

$$\mathbf{e}_o = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{n}_c \times \mathbf{n}_d + \mathbf{s}_c \times \mathbf{s}_d + \mathbf{a}_c \times \mathbf{a}_d) \quad (28)$$

As is explained in [3], the CLIK solution using axis-angle method is expected to perform better than the solution using the two previous methods since this uses the geometric Jacobian instead of the analytical Jacobian, thus avoiding the possibility of representation singularities.

It is necessary considering that this method is valid only if $\sin(\theta)$ is equal (almost the same) than θ .

- Quaternion

The quaternion represents the orientation as a vector that corresponds to

$$\mathbf{Q} = \{\eta, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}\} = \eta + \epsilon_x \cdot \mathbf{i} + \epsilon_y \cdot \mathbf{j} + \epsilon_z \cdot \mathbf{k} \quad (29)$$

Assuming that $\mathbf{Q}_d = \{\eta_d, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_d\}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_c = \{\eta_c, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c\}$ represent the unitary quaternions associated with the already mentioned \mathbf{R}_d and \mathbf{R}_c respectively, the orientation error $\mathbf{e}_o = \{error_4, error_5, error_6\}$ can be expressed in terms of the $\Delta\mathbf{Q} = \{\Delta\eta, \Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon}\}$ where

$$\Delta\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}_d * \mathbf{Q}_c^{-1} \quad (30)$$

With this procedure, $\Delta\mathbf{Q} = \{1, 0\}$ if and only \mathbf{R}_d and \mathbf{R}_c are aligned. Hence, the orientation error can be computed with

$$\mathbf{e}_o = \Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \eta_c \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_d - \eta_d \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c - S(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_d) \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_c \quad (31)$$

where $S(\cdot)$ is the skew-symmetric operator.

3. THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHOSEN IK METHOD

The CLIK algorithm that can be observed at Fig. 8, is first-order differential kinematics, which converts from the task space to the joints space velocities. There is also a second-order CLIK, the algorithm for the second-order differential kinematics, which provides the analogous relation between acceleration. And the zero-order CLIK, the algorithm for the inverse kinematics, which relates the task poses with joints positions.

First-order CLIK algorithm needs the values of the desired task position s_k and task velocity \dot{s}_k that the robot has to reach and the current joints configuration to obtain the next position q_k and velocity \dot{q}_k at which the joints must be moved so that the end-effector to arrive at the desired pose and velocity

$$\dot{q}_k = J^+ (\dot{s}_k + K * error) \quad (32)$$

In this chapter, the method for solving the IK problem has been chosen. After the research carried out in the section 2.2 of the State of the art, no IK library with CLIK method has been found. So, implementing a new IK library is necessary. The creation process is described in next chapter.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

As it is said before, the objective robot for FCC has 11 DOF, and it is going to be fully designed by CERN engineers. But all along the first development and test process of the FCC robot, the idea is using the UR10e robot from Universal Robots, which has 6 DOF, for the last 6 degrees of the 11 and building the parts for other 5 DOF, as it can be seeing in Fig. 9. But during the CLIK development and tests, the built parts of the FCC prototype are not ready, so all the process is going to be implemented only for the UR10e.

Fig. 9. Prototype of FCC robot (a) Scheme. (b) Simulation figure.

4.1. Architecture of the CERN Robotic Framework

The implementation of this Inverse Kinematics method should be done inside an existent framework, the CERN Robotic Framework (CRF), which is a set of programs developed in different projects and stored in a GitLab repository.

GitLab [17] is a programming management tool. The main software developers in the section are in charge of the master branch and the rest of the developers program in other branches that are uploaded to the master when they are reviewed and pass successfully all the tests.

So, the development of this project is carried out in different branches and modifying the master little by little.

First of all, complementary codes that will be needed in the Close Loop Inverse Kinematics program should be written, leaving the CLIK for one of the last tasks to do.

In each task, the first of all has been planning the structure of the new program/s, then a new branch on GitLab has been created for implementing the codes and at least, the tests. Before the merging with the master of the CRF, an iterative process of revisions and corrections with the external supervisors of this MDFP (and other programmers in charge of it) has been done.

Before creating CLIK program, other needed blocks have to be coded. These are, in order of implementation: Jacobian, Forward Kinematics and Error Computation.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

In Fig. 10 a full perspective of the set of codes that are needed and the relation between them can be observed.

Fig. 10. Relation between the programs.

The CRF is divided in a lot of modules. As can be seen in the Fig. 11, the programs carried out in this project are distributed in different folders inside the modules Math, Robots and Utility. In Fig. 10, each colour belongs to a folder. The blue codes correspond to the RobotArmInverseKinematics folder and the purple to RobotArm, both inside Robot module. The codes that belong to the ErrorComputation folder inside Math module are in green. Finally, the ones that are related to the Utility module inside Types folder are in pink.

Fig. 11. CRF modules used in this project.

Also, in Fig. 10 the intensity of the colour and the thickness of the edges differentiate the codes that are already implemented, with soft colours, from the ones that are carried out in this project, with intense colours and thicker edges.

Even there are some programs written in Python and other languages in the CRF, the majority is developed in C++, currently the 87%.

As [18] explains, C++ is an open ISO-standardized language since 1998. When it is optimized, C++ is of the fastest in the world since it is a compiled language. It is upwards compatible with C, so C libraries can be used without or with minimum modifications. Also, it is very portable, because is one of the most frequently used languages, since there is a wide range of compilers that run on many different platforms that support it.

So, the programs developed in this project are implemented with 2017 C++ standard. As in the rest of CRF programs, the methodology used is the Object-Oriented Programming (OOP), which create templates called classes from which instances, known as objects, can be created. This methodology allows code to be reused in remarkable ways avoiding the repetition of code and is meant to be easy to understand with its clear structure.

In this way, implementing a new block (folder) inside a module is easy, by creating the new classes and the launchers. The architecture inside each folder is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Folder structure.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The first file that each folder has is the CMake file that in the CRF is always called `DependenciesAndImplementations.cmake`, where the modules and libraries dependencies are checked during the compilation process. As it is explained in [19]:

“CMake is an open-source, cross-platform family of tools designed to build, test and package software. CMake is used to control the software compilation process using simple platform and compiler independent configuration files and generate native makefiles and workspaces that can be used in the compiler environment of your choice”.

As can be seen at Fig. 12, each folder has at least one of this configuration files called `CMakeLists.txt` for controlling the built process. Also, each tests subfolder has one of this configuration files.

To validate all the functionalities of the class implemented and to avoid future errors due to changes in the code, some unit tests are created with the Google Test library [20]. This verifies the correct operation of the class independently of the other codes of the framework.

In order to facilitate the reuse of the classes in multiple files, the class declarations are written in header files (HPP extension) inside the include subfolder.

If inside one folder there is more than one class that shares the same methods, a new class is created to be the parent from where the other classes inherit the functions. This template class is called `Interface` and to differentiate it the file name starts with "I".

Each class has two kinds of members that can be declared: the variables, which are called attributes, and the functions, also called methods. There is a special method called constructor that is automatically executed when an object of a class is created. To indicate which access has each member of the class, there are three access specifiers: `public`, that allows the access to the members from outside the class; `private`, that deny the access to the member from outside the class; and `protected`, that means that members only can be accessed from outside the class in inherited classes.

The definition of the classes methods is done in the source files (CPP extension) ubicated inside `scr` folder.

Sample files are small main codes (CPP extension) where the object/s created in this folder are used. These small examples help the user to understand completely the functioning of the object creation and its utilization.

In the following subsections there is a brief description of utilised external libraries, and also of the CRF programs used but not implemented in this project.

4.2. External libraries

In this project two external libraries are used: Eigen and the C++ Mathematical Expression Toolkit (ExprTk).

- Eigen library

It is a C++ template library for a linear algebra: matrices, vectors, numerical solvers, and related algorithms, as it is explained in [21]. Eigen is versatile, since it supports all matrix sizes, all standard numeric types, and various matrix decompositions and geometry features. It is also fast, reliable and easy to use for C++ programmers.

The two main reasons why Eigen is utilized in this project are because it is already used in the CRF, so all the computers that use the CRF have this library installed, and its characteristics fits with the requirements of the project, where it is used mainly for matrices treatment.

- C++ Mathematical Expression Toolkit library

ExprTk is a C++ library for parsing mathematical expressions, what means that it is capable to translate text mathematical expressions to understandable elements for the C++ compiler like variables, operators, functions, etc.

As it is explained in [22], ExprTk is simple to use, easy to integrate and extremely run-time efficient, how it is demonstrated in the study [23], where the evaluation time of several parsers is compared, taking care also of the number of fails during the parsing.

The functioning of this library is explained with the help of de diagram shown at Fig. 13. The first element to take care about is the Symbol Table, where the external variables, vectors, strings, constants are defined. The second element is the Expression, to which the Symbol Table must be associated. The third important element is the Parser, that creates an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) from the text mathematical expression in String format and the symbols that have been associated to the Expression. The AST is stored in the Expression, who can be evaluated as many times as needed.

In order to evaluate the Expression with different values of the variables, repeating all this process is not needed. It is only needed to assign the new values to the variables and evaluate the Expression again.

Fig. 13. Diagram of the ExprTK library functioning [22].

This library has been chosen for this project because it is the one that best satisfies our necessities, among which is the efficiency and the fact that it is prepared for being parsed once and being able to evaluate it many times.

- Nlohmann JSON library

In the CRF, the content defined by the user is written in JSON files. So, in this project, like it is necessary that the user provides some information, a JSON library is needed.

There are a lot of JSON libraries in the market, having each one different characteristics. Nlohmann [24] is a C++ JSON library with a really intuitive syntax, and easy to integrate with a header file. It is also reliable since it has been tested covering the 100% of the code.

Nlohmann JSON library is the one used in this project since is the one that is already used in the CRF and none of its features act against the objectives of the project.

4.3. Useful CRF programs

As it is said before, some of the programs already implemented in the CRF are used in this project.

- Types

Most of them belong to the Utility module and are located in Types folder (Fig. 14) since are treated as variable types. These are the classes JointsPosition, JointsVelocity, JointsAcceleration, TaskPosition, TaskVelocity, and TaskAcceleration.

JointsPosition, JointsVelocity and JointsAcceleration are sets of values which size corresponds to the number of joints of the robot. Each component corresponds respectively to the position, velocity and acceleration of each joint of the robot that are associated with.

TaskPosition represents the task space, the position of the robot end-effector. It is composed by 3 elements that corresponds to the position and other elements that represents the orientation. The orientation can be set and requested in Cardan, Euler ZXZ, axis-angle, quaternions or rotation matrix.

TaskVelocity and TaskAcceleration respectively corresponds to the velocity and acceleration of the robot end-effector. They are formed by 3 values for the linear velocity and acceleration and 3 values for the angular velocity and acceleration.

- RobotArm

Another class that is used in this project is RobotArmConfiguration. This class is in charge of parsing all the information about a robot arm stored inside a JSON file, so that other programs that needs this information could made use of it.

The JSON configuration files are an organised way to let the user introduce all the specific information about the robot. Thanks to this all the programs can be implemented in a generic way for being used with different kinds of robots and ask through the configuration files the required information about the robot.

4.4. Programs implemented for CLIK

Once the CRF classes to be used in the project have been exposed, the following sections will explain the programs written in chronological order.

Fig. 14. Types folder structure.

4.4.1. Jacobian

In the CRF, Jacobian class is implemented as a type of variable inside Utility module, as the previously introduced Joints and Task classes. All of them can be observed in Fig. 14.

The structure of this class can be seen in TABLE I.

TABLE I
Structure of Jacobian class

Method name	Inputs	Outputs
Public		
Jacobian (Ctor)	nlohman::json jsonConfig std::vector<double> lAxValues std::vector<double> lAyValues std::vector<double> lAzValues	-
Jacobian (Ctor)	Jacobian other	-
Jacobian (Dtor)	-	-
evaluate	JointsPosition qValues	Eigen::MatrixXd JMatrix
getKinematicManipulability	JointsPosition qValues	std::optional<double> - std::nullopt - kinematicManipulability
operator=	Jacobian other	Jacobian j
operator==	Jacobian other	bool true/false
operator!=	Jacobian other	bool true/false
operator<<	std::ostream os Jacobian j	std::ostream os
Private		
transformJson2String	-	std::string finalMathExpression
createMathExpressionTree	-	-

➤ Constructor

The Jacobian object can be formed from different methods: passing the already computed Jacobian matrix, creating it from another Jacobian object, obtaining it by Denavit-Hatemberg method or other techniques.

A brief explanation of each method is presented.

- Passing the computed math expressions of Jacobian matrix

The first implemented way of constructing a Jacobian is passing the mathematical expressions of all the Jacobian matrix components as a JSON variable, and then using a parser (ExprTK library) to make understand the mathematical expression to the computer.

The inputs of this Jacobian constructor are:

- jsonConfig, the set of mathematical expressions that conforms the Jacobian matrix in a JSON variable,
- lAxValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the X axis direction,
- lAyValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the Y axis direction, and
- lAzValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the Z axis direction.

The four variables have been declared as private attributes in the Jacobian.hpp file since all of them are used in the different functions of the class.

The content of `jsonConfig` should follow the proper structure to be understood in C++. Each one of the mathematical expressions is in the assigned position according to the row and the column to which it belongs. The mathematical expressions that make up the Jacobian matrix must be obtained previously by methods external to the CRF and are outside the work of this MDFP.

As it is said in the subsection 4.2, the `ExprTk` parser needs the mathematical expression in `STRING` format, so to convert it from `JSON` to `STRING` the method `transformJson2String` is created. It does the conversion making the needed changes for the parser understanding and returns the math expression in `STRING` format ready to be used in the parser.

The mathematical expression has several variables, which are associated to the `ExprTk` Symbol Table inside the function `createMathExpressionTree`:

- `J`, that is a vector where the parsed mathematical expressions of the Jacobian matrix components are going to be stored,
- `lANx`, that is the length between the two joints of this N link in the X axe direction, being N the number of the link to which corresponds,
- `lANy`, that is the length between the two joints of this N link in the Y axe direction, being N the number of the link to which corresponds,
- `lANz`, that is the length between the two joints of this N link in the Z axe direction, being N the number of the link to which corresponds, and
- `qN`, that is the N joint angle, being N the number of the link to which corresponds.

The variable `J` is a vector and not a matrix because `ExprTk` library doesn't allow the possibility of working with matrix structures, so one of the changes that is done in `transformJson2String` method mentioned before is converting the Jacobian structure from matrix to vector in row-major order.

In this constructor, as it is said before, the values of the lengths between the robot joints of the three axes (`lAxValues`, `lAyValues` and `lAzValues`) are given as inputs because they are constant independently from the Joints configuration. Due to this reason, the values are assigned to the corresponding variables (`lANx`, `lANy` and `lANz`) of the parser Symbol Table inside `createMathExpressionTree`, being ready for the evaluation of the mathematical expressions all the needed times.

When the constructor finishes, the AST is saved in the `Expression` variable, that is declared also as an attribute of the Jacobian class, as well as the Symbol Table. The variables `qN` wait until the `evaluate` function for being assigned with values since these parameters are variable and the resulting numerical Jacobian changes according to these.

- From another Jacobian object

This kind of constructor is called Copy Constructor and it basically copies automatically all the attributes from the input Jacobian object, making a copy of this.

In most of the cases it could be done automatically, but not in this class due to the `ExprTk` library use since this library doesn't allow copy operations.

For solving that, the procedure was to create the elements related to the `ExprTk` library again: the Symbol Table, the Expression and the Parser, using the function `createMathExpressionTree`.

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- Others

The class is prepared for accept future new constructors that uses other methods to create Jacobian objects.

- evaluate method

In this function, as its name says, the mathematical expressions parsed in the constructor are evaluated with the given joints angles (qValues) for obtaining the resulting numerical Jacobian Vector, J.

For the moment the Jacobian is a Vector, because as it is said before, the ExprTk library cannot work with matrices. So, for returning to the user the Jacobian in matrix format, in this function the Jacobian is converted from vector to matrix, the inverse procedure that is done in the constructor inside the transformJson2String method.

- getKinematicManipulability method

The purpose of this function is to calculate the kinematic manipulability of a robot (11) is the expression used for the computation, being $J(\mathbf{q})$ the Jacobian matrix evaluated with \mathbf{q} joint angles, given in the input JointsPosition variable, qValues.

Like this function only has as input the positions of the joints, inside the function calling the evaluate function is necessary to obtain the numerical Jacobian matrix.

The result of this function is false, if due to any problem, the solution cannot be obtained, and true in the case the solution is obtained without any problem. In this last case, also the numeric solution of the kinematic manipulability is returned. This is the behaviour of the function `std::optional<variableType>`, that returns true or false depending on the success of the task and if it is successful it also returns the variable whose type is indicated between the angle brackets.

- operator=

As it is said at the beginning, Jacobian class is treated as a type of variable inside the CRF, so as other type variable, some useful operators are also defined.

This operator makes one Jacobian variable equal to another.

With this operator there is the same problem as with the Copy Constructor because ExprTk library doesn't allow either this assignation. So, the procedure for solving this problem is the same: creating again the Symbol Table, the Expression and the Parser, using the function `createMathExpressionTree`.

- operator==

This operator compares two Jacobian variables for knowing if they are equal, returning true, and returning false if this is not the case.

For this case, realizing a comparison is complicated, since the information inside Jacobian variables is a group of mathematical expressions, not numbers, since the Jacobian matrix is not evaluated, and different written expressions can result in the same Jacobian.

So, the comparison operation is between the two STRING expressions. True result is always correct. But it should be noted that not all the time the comparison returns false, the Jacobian will be different.

And also, the 3 vector inputs of the lengths between joints (`lAxValues`, `lAyValues` and `lAzValues`) are compared for testing that are the same.

It was tried to implement the comparison between the three schemes resulting of the parsing, but it was not possible due to a bug in the ExprTk library.

➤ `operator!=`

In this case the objective of the comparison is to know if the two Jacobian variables are different. And the problem with the result is the opposite to the `operator==`. When it returns false it always is correct, but the true return doesn't mean that the Jacobian will be different for the same reason explained before.

➤ `operator<<`

This operator is used for printing. The result of the implementation can be seen in Fig. 15.

These are the mathematical expressions that are given as input of the constructor inside `jsonConfig`.

4.4.2. Forward Kinematics

Like it happens with Jacobian, Forward Kinematics class can be implemented for computing its expressions inside the program with Denavit-Hatemberg technique between others, or directly implementing it for reading the FK expressions computed outside the framework.

This second option, called `MathExprFK`, is the class carried out in this project for the Forward Kinematics, leaving the opportunity to implement in the future more methods in other classes.

`MathExprFK` class is part of `RobotArmKinematics` folder (Fig. 16) inside `Robots` module. In this case, the interface file, `IForwardKinematics.hpp`, is created inside `include` subfolder with the intention of being the template for the method carried out in this project and for the future new classes.

Even thought for this project, only FK in position is needed, also FK in velocity and acceleration are defined and implemented. Since one of the objectives of the project is the generalization of the programs implemented, velocity and acceleration FK have been developed because they will be used in future applications.

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```

J[0][0] = cos(q1) * (((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3) + LA3z) * sin(q2) + ((-LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) + sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * cos(q2)) - sin(q1) * (LA6x * cos(q5) + LA2x - LA3x + LA4x))

J[0][1] = (((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3) + LA3z) * cos(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * sin(q2)) * sin(q1)

J[0][2] = (((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3)) * cos(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * sin(q2)) * sin(q1)

J[0][3] = -(((LA5z * cos(q4) - LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)) * cos(q3) - (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3)) * cos(q2) + ((-LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) + sin(q3) * (LA5z * cos(q4) + LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)))) * sin(q2)) * sin(q1)

J[0][4] = LA6x * (((sin(q4) * sin(q3) - cos(q4) * cos(q3)) * cos(q2) + sin(q2) * (cos(q4) * sin(q3) + sin(q4) * cos(q3))) * sin(q1) * cos(q5) - cos(q1) * sin(q5))

J[0][5] = 0

J[1][0] = (((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3) + LA3z) * sin(q2) + ((-LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) + sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * cos(q2)) * sin(q1) + cos(q1) * (LA6x * cos(q5) + LA2x - LA3x + LA4x))

J[1][1] = -cos(q1) * (((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3) + LA3z) * cos(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * sin(q2)) * sin(q1)

J[1][2] = -(((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3)) * cos(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * sin(q2)) * cos(q1)

J[1][3] = -cos(q1) * (((LA5z * cos(q4) + LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3)) * cos(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA5z * cos(q4) + LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)))) * sin(q2))

J[1][4] = -LA6x * cos(q5) * ((sin(q4) * sin(q3) - cos(q4) * cos(q3)) * cos(q2) + sin(q2) * (cos(q4) * sin(q3) + sin(q4) * cos(q3))) * cos(q1) + sin(q1) * sin(q5))

J[1][5] = 0

J[2][0] = 0

J[2][1] = ((-LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * cos(q4) - LA4z) * cos(q3) + (-LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3) - LA3z) * sin(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * cos(q2))

J[2][2] = ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z)) * cos(q2) - sin(q2) * ((LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * cos(q4) + LA4z) * cos(q3) + (LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3))

J[2][3] = ((-LA5z * cos(q4) - LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)) * cos(q3) + (-LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) + LA5z * sin(q4)) * sin(q3)) * sin(q2) + ((LA6x * cos(q4) * sin(q5) - LA5z * sin(q4)) * cos(q3) - sin(q3) * (LA5z * cos(q4) + LA6x * sin(q4) * sin(q5)))) * cos(q2)

J[2][4] = -cos(q5) * (sin(q4) * (sin(q2) * sin(q3) - cos(q2) * cos(q3)) - (sin(q2) * cos(q3) + cos(q2) * sin(q3)) * cos(q4)) * LA6x

J[2][5] = 0

J[3][0] = 0

J[3][1] = cos(q1)

J[3][2] = cos(q1)

J[3][3] = cos(q1)

J[3][4] = -sin(q1) * (sin(q4) * (sin(q2) * sin(q3) - cos(q2) * cos(q3)) - (sin(q2) * cos(q3) + cos(q2) * sin(q3)) * cos(q4))

J[3][5] = sin(q5) * ((sin(q4) * sin(q3) - cos(q4) * cos(q3)) * cos(q2) + sin(q2) * (cos(q4) * sin(q3) + sin(q4) * cos(q3))) * sin(q1) + cos(q1) * cos(q5))

J[4][0] = 0

J[4][1] = sin(q1)

J[4][2] = sin(q1)

J[4][3] = sin(q1)

J[4][4] = (sin(q4) * (sin(q2) * sin(q3) - cos(q2) * cos(q3)) - (sin(q2) * cos(q3) + cos(q2) * sin(q3)) * cos(q4)) * cos(q1)

J[4][5] = -sin(q5) * ((sin(q4) * sin(q3) - cos(q4) * cos(q3)) * cos(q2) + sin(q2) * (cos(q4) * sin(q3) + sin(q4) * cos(q3))) * cos(q1) + sin(q1) * cos(q5))

J[5][0] = 1

J[5][1] = 0

J[5][2] = 0

J[5][3] = 0

J[5][4] = (-cos(q2) * sin(q3) - sin(q2) * cos(q3)) * sin(q4) + (-sin(q2) * sin(q3) + cos(q2) * cos(q3)) * cos(q4)

J[5][5] = ((sin(q2) * cos(q3) + cos(q2) * sin(q3)) * cos(q4) + (-sin(q2) * sin(q3) + cos(q2) * cos(q3)) * sin(q4)) * sin(q5)

```

Fig. 15. Jacobian mathematical expressions of UR10e robot.

Fig. 16. RobotArmKinematics folder structure.

The structure of MathExprFK class can be seen in Fig. 16. The methods `getPosition`, `getVelocity` and `getAcceleration` are defined in the interface so they will be functions also of the future FK classes implemented with other methods.

TABLE II
Structure of MathExprFK class

Method name	Inputs	Outputs
Public		
MathExprFK (Ctor)	nlohman::json jsonConfig std::vector<double> lAxValues std::vector<double> lAyValues std::vector<double> lAzValues	-
MathExprFK (Dtor)	-	-
getPosition	JointsPosition qValues	std::optional<TaskPosition> - std::nullopt - position
getVelocity	JointsPosition qValues JointsVelocity qdValues	std::optional<TaskVelocity> - std::nullopt - velocity
getAcceleration	JointsPosition qValues JointsVelocity qdValues JointsAcceleration qddValues	std::optional<TaskAcceleration> - std::nullopt - acceleration
Private		
parse	exprtk::expression<double> std::string linear std::string angular	std::optional< exprtk::expression<double>> - std::nullopt - parsedMathExpression

➤ Constructor

The process of the MathExprFK constructor is more or less the same of Jacobian constructor: passing the already computed FK expressions in JSON format and then using the parser of ExprTK library. For this reason, the arguments of the MathExprFK constructor are almost the same than the inputs of the Jacobian constructor:

- jsonConfig, the set of mathematical expressions of forward kinematics. It can contain the expressions of position, velocity and acceleration, but it is not mandatory having the three of them.
- lAxValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the X axis direction,
- lAyValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the Y axis direction, and
- lAzValues, a vector of the lengths between the robot joints in the Z axis direction.

Also in this class, the four variables have been declared as private attributes, this time in the MathExprFK.hpp file.

For the same robot, the values assigned to the variables of the lengths between de axes in FK are the same as in Jacobian.

As in FK the parser used is the same, the content of jsonConfig also should follow the proper structure to be understood in C++. But in this case there is only one function, called parse, that transforms the JSON to STRING and creates the Symbol Table and the Expression variables of the ExprTK parser library.

In this class these two processes cannot be separated because this method performs different actions according to the type of FK: position, velocity or acceleration. This is due to two aspects:

- the duality that FK has, since there are expressions of the linear or the angular magnitude, and
- the way of representing each FK, since the three linear magnitudes are usually represented with 3 parameters: position (in cartesian space), linear velocity and linear acceleration. But the orientation representation changes depending on the magnitude:
 - position can be depicted with the rotation matrix (size 3x3) or with quaternions (4 parameters), but
 - velocity and acceleration are represented with the angular velocity and acceleration respectively (3 values).

As it happens in Jacobian, when the constructor finishes, the AST of each magnitude is saved in each corresponding Expression variable, that are declared as attributes of the MathExprFK class, as well as all the Symbol Tables.

➤ `getPosition` method

In this function, the mathematical expressions of FK parsed in the constructor are evaluated with the given joints position (`qValues`) for obtaining the resulting numerical FK in a `TaskPosition` variable that, as it is explained in the subsection 4.3, comprises position and orientation.

➤ `getVelocity` method

In this case, the evaluations are done in the linear and angular velocity ExprTK library Expressions. Being necessary in this case not only the joints position (`qValues`), but also the joints velocity (`qdValues`). And returning a `TaskVelocity`.

➤ `getAcceleration` method

This function evaluates the linear and the angular acceleration. For the evaluation it needs the joints acceleration (`qddValues`), the joints velocity (`qdValues`) and the joints position (`qValues`). The result is a `TaskAcceleration` variable.

4.4.3. Error Computation

At CLIK, the error computed is defined as the difference between the desired and the real pose of the robot end-effector. The set of position and orientation is what there is implemented in the CRF as a `TaskPosition` variable, as it is explained in the subsection 4.3.

The calculation of the error between two `TaskPosition` variables is not implemented as a class, because the OOP does not fit in this case.

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The best way to implement this process is with four functions, one for each orientation representation method that can be used to execute this computation: Cardan, Euler, axis-angle and quaternion. The orientation representation used gives the name to the function, being their names respectively: `getErrorCardan`, `getErrorEulerZXZ`, `getErrorAxisAngle` and `getErrorQuaternion`.

The structure of the four functions is the same. They have two arguments, the two `TaskPosition` variables that represents the desired and the real pose of the robot end-effector, and they return an array of 6 values.

Inside each function the `TaskPosition` values are requested in the position and the needed representation of the orientation. Later, the corresponding calculus take place and the result is returned.

These functions have been defined and implemented in the `TaskPositionError` files ubicated inside `ErrorComputation` folder, that is part of the `Math` module, as can be observed at Fig. 17.

Fig. 17. `ErrorComputation` folder structure.

4.5. CLIK

Once all the programs needed for CLIK are created, this IK algorithm can be implemented. As is shown at Fig. 16, CLIK shares RobotArmKinematics folder with MathExprFK inside Robots module.

As it is explained in the chapter 3, there are different IK algorithms. CLIK is a first order one, but zero and second order are also common and could be implemented in the future. So, respecting our objective of openness to new implementations, interfaces for the three orders have been created. They are called respectively:

- I0thOrderInverseKinematics.hpp,
- I1stOrderInverseKinematics.hpp, and
- I2ndOrderInverseKinematics.hpp.

The three of them have two functions: `getResults` which returns only the corresponding information about the joints according to the order and a flag about how successful the result has been; and `getExtendedResults` that returns, apart from these both, more information about the internal processes that can be an interesting object of study. The structure of the three interfaces is shown at TABLE III.

TABLE III
Structure of Inverse Kinematics Interface classes

	Method name	Inputs	Outputs
	Public		
0 th Order	I0thOrderInverseKinematics (Dtor)	-	-
	getResults	TaskPosition z	std::tuple< JointsPosition q, ResultFlags flag>
	getExtendedResults	TaskPosition z	Results0thOrderIK extendedResult
1 st Order	I1stOrderInverseKinematics (Dtor)	-	-
	getResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd	std::tuple< JointsPosition q, JointsVelocity qd, ResultFlags flag>
	getExtendedResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd	Results1stOrderIK extendedResult
2 nd Order	I2ndOrderInverseKinematics (Dtor)	-	-
	getResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd TaskAcceleration zdd	std::tuple< JointsPosition q, JointsVelocity qd, JoitsAcceleration qdd, ResultFlags flag>
	getExtendedResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd TaskAcceleration zdd	Results2ndOrderIK extendedResult

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The needed arguments of both methods are the same. According to the order, the inputs are the end-effector next desired position, velocity and/or acceleration that want to be reached from the current magnitudes of the end-effector.

Both methods always return the corresponding computed information about the joints, independently from the message given by the flag. Then, the user is who has to decide, depending on the flag, if the result is usable or not. In this way, the user is able to run offline the IK of a full trajectory and process the results, erasing or changing the not valid results.

The different kinds of flags have been defined inside ResultFlag.hpp file. These are, arranged from positive to the worst case:

- success, in the case the desired end-effector position has been achieved correctly;
- lowManipulability, when the robot is close to a singularity. This case is only a warning, so the program can continue with this kind of result;
- endEffectorToleranceViolation, in the case the desired end-effector position has not been achieved inside the desired position tolerance. It might be due to a violation of the robot workspace or other reasons. This one is already considered an error, what means that the program cannot use the resulting joints information;
- maxComputationTimeViolation, in the moment it takes more time than the required. This is also considered an error; and
- workspaceViolation, when the end-effector desired position is not reachable for the robot.

This arrangement of the flags also indicates from low to high the importance and priority of each error or warning flag, since only one kind of result can be given and some of them could be happening at the same time, what means that one flag can include others that are explained before. For example, if ResultFlag is workspaceViolation, also there is possible that computation time and/or the end-effector tolerance will be violated and/or the manipulability will be low. But if ResultFlag is endEffectorToleranceViolation, neither maxComputationTimeViolation neither workspaceViolation will happen.

For returning all the information of getExtendedResults function in each order, three classes with structure format have been created, one for each order, called respectively: Results0thOrderIK, Results1stOrderIK and Results2ndOrderIK. For avoiding the repetition of code, the Results1stOrderIK inherits from Results0thOrderIK, and the Results2ndOrderIK inherits from Results1stOrderIK. Thanks to this, as it can be observed at TABLE IV, inside Results2ndOrderIK there is only necessity to declare and define the functions related to the acceleration, since the methods of velocity are declared in Results1stOrderIK and the rest in Results0thOrderIK, being all of them accessible to Results2ndOrderIK.

For each variable that needs to be stored, two methods have been created, one for saving the information and the other for extracting it. These variables are private attributes of the corresponding class.

Apart from these functions, the Empty Constructor and the Destructor, in each class also the Copy Constructor and the assignment operator (`operator=`) have been defined and implemented, since they are very useful allowing the creation of a new object from another or assign one object to other already created.

TABLE IV
Structure of IK Results classes

	Method name	Inputs	Outputs
Public			
0 th Order	Results0thOrderIK (Ctor)	-	-
	Results0thOrderIK (Ctor)	Results0thOrderIK other	-
	Results0thOrderIK (Dtor)	-	-
	operator=	Results0thOrderIK other	Results0thOrderIK results
	zDesired	TaskPosition z	-
	zDesired	-	TaskPosition z
	qResult	JointsPosition q	-
	qResult	-	JointsPosition q
	flag	ResultFlags flag	-
	flag	-	ResultFlags flag
	zError	std::array<double, 6> zError	-
	zError	-	std::array<double, 6> zError
1 st Order	Results1stOrderIK (Ctor)	-	-
	Results1stOrderIK (Ctor)	Results1stOrderIK other	-
	Results1stOrderIK (Dtor)	-	-
	operator=	Results1stOrderIK other	Results1stOrderIK results
	zdDesired	TaskPosition zd	-
	zdDesired	-	TaskPosition zd
	qdResult	JointsPosition qd	-
	qdResult	-	JointsPosition qd
2 nd Order	Results2ndOrderIK (Ctor)	-	-
	Results2ndOrderIK (Ctor)	Results2ndOrderIK other	-
	Results2ndOrderIK (Dtor)	-	-
	operator=	Results2ndOrderIK other	Results2ndOrderIK results
	zddDesired	TaskPosition zdd	-
	zddDesired	-	TaskPosition zdd
	qddResult	JointsPosition qdd	-
	qddResult	-	JointsPosition qdd

CLIK is a class that inherits from I1stInverseKinematics, so, as can be observed at TABLE V, it has the same methods of the interface plus the constructor and another private method. It computes the IK in a close loop manner returning the position and velocity of the joints from specified values of the end-effector pose and velocities.

TABLE V
Structure of CLIK class

Method name	Inputs	Outputs
Public		
CLIK (Ctor)	JointsPosition qInitial std::chrono::microseconds time std::shared_ptr<RobotArmConfiguration> robotArmConf TaskPosition cardanErrorTolerance double k double w0 double alpha0	-
CLIK (Dtor)	-	-
getResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd	std::tuple< JointsPosition q, JointsVelocity qd, ResultFlags flag>
getExtendedResults	TaskPosition z TaskVelocity zd	Results1stOrderIK extendedResult
Private		
getVelocityIK	TaskPosition zd JointsPosition qCurrent	std::pair< JointsVelocity qd, ResultFlags flag>

➤ Constructor

All the elements that are going to be constant for the IK computing of a robot are arguments of the constructor, since in this moment it is important to save computation time during the execution of the getting results functions. They are:

- `qInitial`, the set of beginning joints position,
- `time`, used in the Euler integral to obtain the joints position from the joints velocity,
- `robotArmConf`, object form `RobotArmConfiguration` class (exposed at subsection 4.3) that contains the Forward Kinematics expressions, the Jacobian expressions and the robot lengths between other parameters,
- `cardanErrorTolerance`, a set of tolerances for the positions in x, y and z coordinates, and the cardan angles. The introduced values must be positive, even if they represent the positive and negative tolerance,
- `k`, the gain that will be applied in the computed error,
- `w0`, the manipulability minimum limit for discriminating the singularities, and
- `alpha0`, the base damping factor.

The last four input parameters of the constructor are optional since they have associated predetermined values.

The processes carried out in this constructor are:

- the assignment of the values introduced through the arguments to their respective class attributes,
- extracting the robot lengths from the robotArmConfiguration object and save them in its attribute,
- extracting the mathematical expressions of Jacobian and FK in JSON format and create the Jacobian object and the MathExprFK object using as arguments for their constructors the corresponding JSON variable and the lengths.

➤ `getResults` method

Inside this function, `getExtendedResults` is run. From the `Results1stOrder` object created, only the joints position, the joints velocity and the flag are selected for being returned.

➤ `getExtendedResults` method

This function run one iteration of the CLIK algorithm developed.

Next, with the help of the flowchart shown at Fig. 18, the implementation of this algorithm, explained theoretically at chapter 3, is detailed.

After checking the inputs, it computes the current end-effector position applying FK to the current joints position, with the already explained `getPosition` method of `MathExprFK` class.

In a loop where this function is called for the first time, the current joints position (`qCurrent`) is the `qInitial` given in the constructor and stored as attribute of the class. As can be seen in the Fig. 18, when the new joints position (`q`) is computed, it is stored in the `qInitial` attribute for being the `qCurrent` of the next execution of the function.

To reset `qInitial`, a new constructor needs to be built.

The following step is the computation of the error between the desired end-effector position (`zDesired`), that is an argument of the function, and the already calculated current end-effector position (`zCurrent`). The orientation representation method used to compute de error is axis angle, so the function used is `getErrorAxisAngle` of `TaskErrorComputation` class.

Next, as can be observed in the schema of Fig. 8 and in the flowchart of Fig. 18, a corrected task velocity, $\dot{s}_{corrected}$, is obtained closing the loop with the error times a gain matrix (`k`), which was set in the constructor, added to the desired task velocity, $\dot{s}_{desired}$,

$$\dot{s}_{corrected} = \dot{s}_{desired} + k * error \quad (33)$$

Then, the joints velocity is obtained applying the function `getVelocityIK` to the task velocity estimated and to the current joints position.

As it is explained at chapter 3, the Inverse Kinematics method used in the algorithm is the damped least-squares pseudo-inverse Jacobian. So, as can be seen at the Fig. 19, the numeric Jacobian matrix is computed with `q` using the `evaluate` method.

Fig. 18. Flowchart of getExtendedResults function.

Fig. 19. Flowchart of getVelocityIK function.

Later, to be able to calculate the damped least-squares pseudo-inverse Jacobian, the damping factor (α) parameter needs to be determined. The value of α depends on the kinematic manipulability, that is computed with the getKinematicManipulability method of Jacobian class.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The value of the computed manipulability also determines how near there are the joint position to a singularity. This limit, as it is explained before, is set by the user in the CLIK constructor. It will be higher or lower depending on the robot movement.

If the manipulability is smaller than the minimum limit, to avoid the singularity, the damping factor is calculated as is shown at (12), and the flag stored is `lowManipulability`. If it is over the limit there is no danger of suffering singularities, so the damping factor is set to zero and the flag stored is `success`.

After this decision, the last steps are calculating the Jacobian and multiplying it to the end-effector velocity (z_d) to obtain the joints velocity (q_d).

Once the joints velocity is obtained, it is integrated to obtain the new joints position (Fig. 18). The integration method applied is backward Euler (13), as it is explained in section 3.

For knowing if this result is inside the workspace and inside the selected tolerance (marked in the constructor), the task space error computed is compared with the tolerance. If it is outside, the flag changes to `endEffectorToleranceViolation`, but if the result remains inside the tolerance, the flag contains the one returned from `getVelocityIK` function.

4.6. Unit tests

As have been explained above, the behaviour of each class has been tested in an independent way. The aspects that are reviewed are listed below:

- check that the input arguments are formatted correctly, and the values introduced are valid,
- confirm that the results obtained with certain inputs are the proper ones, and
- create the failure situations for reviewing that the error messages appear.

5. TESTS AND RESULTS

As it is explained at the beginning of chapter 4, all the tests are carried out on the UR10e robot, since the FCC robot is still not available.

5.1. Test environments

Before testing with the real robot, all the experiments have been simulated first on the UR Graphical Programming Environment (GPA), which is shown at Fig. 20.

Fig. 20. UR Graphical Programming Environment.

As the operative system used for the development of the project is Ubuntu 20.04, the version of the GPA is the offline UR SIM for Linux 5.9.4 – E-series.

All the simulations are executed in the same PC employed for the implementation of the project, a TTL Tekno Pro whose characteristics are shown at TABLE VI.

TABLE VI
TTL Tekno Pro PC characteristics

Characteristics	Description
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz with 4 cores
RAM memory	4 GB
Operating System	Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS
Kernel	Linux 5.13.0-48 SMP
Architecture	x86-64

Once the experiment is simulated successfully, it is tested in the real environment.

5. TESTS AND RESULTS

The working station for the real robot testing can be observed at Fig. 21. The main elements that compose it are:

- the industrial robot model UR10e from Universal Robots, whose characteristics [25] are exposed at TABLE VII,
- the controller of the UR10e robot OEM Control Box, whose characteristics are shown [26] at TABLE VIII,
- the 24 V power supply for the controller, and
- the FCC PC (TABLE IX), that is the computer used to control the robot.

Fig. 21. UR10e testing station.

TABLE VII
UR10e robot characteristics

Characteristics	Description
Power consumption	Approx. 350 W using a typical program / Maximum average 615 W
Maximum payload	10 kg
Maximum reach	1300 mm
Degrees of freedom	6 rotating joints DOF
Enclosure type	IP54
Robot mounting	Any orientation
Footprint	Ø 190 mm
Weight	33,5 kg

TABLE VIII
OEM Control Box characteristics for UR10e robot

Characteristics	Description
I/O power supply	24 V 2 A
Communication	Control frequency: 500 Hz
Input voltage	DC Model: 24-48 V DC
Size (width x high x depth)	451 mm x 168 mm x 150 mm
Weight	DC Model: 4.3 kg

TABLE IX
FCC PC characteristics

Characteristics	Description
CPU	Intel(R) Atom(TM) Processor E3950 @ 1.60GHz with 4 cores
RAM memory	8 GB
Operating System	Ubuntu 20.04.1 LTS
Kernel	Linux 5.9.1-rt20 SMP PREEMPT_RT
Architecture	x86-64

5.2. Testing program

A control program has been written for testing the correct behaviour of the CLIK code implemented.

The structure of this program is exposed in the flowchart of the Fig. 22.

Reading and parsing the configuration file, the program obtains the needed information to connect with the simulator or with the real robot, also the mathematical expressions of the Jacobian matrix and of the pose forward kinematics, and the lengths of the robot links needed to compute them.

Fig. 22. Flowchart of the experiment control program.

This code uses other CRF programs already implemented as the Universal Robots Real-Time Data Exchange (RTDE) class ubicated inside UniversalRobots folder of the Robots method and the Spline curve generator ubicated in the GeometricMethods folder of the Maths method.

- UniversalRobots

The class UniversalRobotsRTDE encompasses all the functions needed for the communication between the computer and the UR10e robot. These functions work both for the simulator and for the real robot.

- GeometricMethods

There are two geometric methods implemented in the CRF to generate two kind of curves: Sinusoid and Spline.

As it is exposed in the Fig. 22, for the experiments of this project, Spline is the curve selected for generating the desired position trajectory. According to [27], “a B-spline curve is a piecewise polynomial curve specified by an arbitrary collection of control points P_j and a nondecreasing sequence of knots t_k , where each individual polynomial segment is defined by the de Boor algorithm. By construction, the k^{th} segment of a degree n B-spline curve:

- lies over the parameter interval $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$,
- has $n + 1$ control points – P_{k-n}, \dots, P_k , and
- depends on $2n$ knots – $t_{k-n+1}, \dots, t_{k+n}$.”

The shape of the Spline curve used in this project is shown at Fig. 23. It starts and ends at the same position. On this way, it is easier to see if the result at the end of the trajectory is correct.

Fig. 23. Spline curve.

The flowchart of the Fig. 22 represents the online version of the testing program since the computation of CLIK is happening in each iteration inside the control loop. Before trying this structure, there was an offline version. In this structure, the inverse kinematics of all the trajectory was computed before entering in the movement control loop.

As it is indicated in the TABLE VIII, the necessary frequency to communicate with the robot controller is 500 Hz. For this reason, each iteration of the control loop must spend 2 ms, as it is exposed at the Fig. 22.

5.3. Execution of the testing program

As it is explained before, each iteration of the control loop has not to overpass the 2 ms.

For this reason, the FCC computer has a Real-Time kernel (TABLE IX). This kernel allows the computer to prioritize the assigned as Real-Time tasks to other computer tasks, avoiding interruptions that could make the control loop spent more than 2 ms.

To assign a program as Real-Time it should be executed with the following command:

```
"sudo chrt -rr 99 ./executable"
```

As the TTL Tekno Pro PC where UR GPA is installed does not have Real-Time kernel, the way to prioritize the executed program is using nice command:

```
"sudo nice -n -20 ./executable"
```

5.4. Experiments

For checking the correct behaviour of the programs developed, 3 simple experiments have been executed.

In the first one, three different end-effector trajectories are executed, obtaining the success flag during the whole trajectory. In the second one, the low manipulability warning flag appears. And in the third experiment, the transition from the successful results to the end-effector tolerance violation error flag can be observed.

In the graphs, this flag is represented by three possible values: 0 – success, 1 – low manipulability, and 2 – end-effector tolerance violation.

In this experiment, the end-effector of the robot follows three kind of trajectories:

- Trajectory 1: Negative linear movement of 10 cm in Z axis
- Trajectory 2: Positive linear movement of 10 cm in Z axis
- Trajectory 3: Positive orientation movement of 90 degrees

These three examples are executed in 21 seconds with a frequency of 500 Hz (10 500 steps).

Then, a fourth experiment with a longer trajectory (negative linear movement) is executed for 121 seconds (60 500 steps).

The last experiment shows a movement more complex composed by spline curves superposed to the initial end-effector pose, in the 3 axis of the linear movement and in the angle.

In all the experiments, the common input arguments used in the CLIK constructor are:

- time = 0.2 ms
- cardanErrorTolerance =
 {0.0001 mm, 0.0001 mm, 0.0001 mm, 0.001 rad, 0.001 rad, 0.001 rad}
- k = 500
- w0 = 0.001
- alpha0 = 0.001

In the following subsections the five experiments are presented, and the results are explained in the next section 5.5.

5.4.1. Experiment 1

The initial joints position for this experiment with the 3 kinds of trajectory is:

{5, -113.48, 67.47, -118.99, 5, 5} degrees

and the initial end-effector pose, with Cardan orientation representation, is:

{-147.83 mm, -304.30 mm, 1 272.27 mm, 0.174 rad, 1.964 rad, -1.949 rad}

- Trajectory 1

The first desired trajectory executed by the robot in this experiment can be observed in the Fig. 24. The trajectory 1 is computed subtracting the corresponding value of the spline curve (with 10 cm of amplitude) to the initial task position in Z axis.

Fig. 24. Experiment 1: Desired end-effector trajectory 1.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 25.

Fig. 25. Experiment 1: Joints position resulting of trajectory 1.

The following Fig. 26 and Fig. 27 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 26. Experiment 1: Simulator results with trajectory 1.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 27. Experiment 1: Real robot results with trajectory 1.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

- Trajectory 2

The second desired trajectory executed by the robot in this experiment can be observed in the Fig. 28. The trajectory 2 is computed adding the corresponding value of the spline curve (with 10 cm of amplitude) to the initial task position in Z axis.

Fig. 28. Experiment 1: Desired end-effector trajectory 2.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 29.

Fig. 29. Experiment 1: Joints position resulting of trajectory 2.

The following Fig. 30 and Fig. 31 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 30. Experiment 1: Simulator results with trajectory 2. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 31. Experiment 1: Real robot results with trajectory 2. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

- Trajectory 3

The third desired trajectory executed by the robot in this experiment can be observed in the Fig. 32. The trajectory 3 is computed adding the corresponding value of the spline curve (with 90 degrees of amplitude) to the initial angle of the axis-angle orientation representation.

Fig. 32. Experiment 1: Desired end-effector trajectory 3.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 33.

Fig. 33. Experiment 1: Joints position resulting of trajectory 3.

The graph of the flag is always 0, which means success flag.

The following Fig. 34 and Fig. 35 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 34. Experiment 1: Simulator results with trajectory 3.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 35. Experiment 1: Real robot results with trajectory 3.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

5.4.2. Experiment 2

This experiment also uses the Trajectory 2, but in this case, the initial joints position is:

{5, -58.95, -47.66, -58.39, 5, 5} degrees

and the initial end-effector pose, with Cardan orientation representation, is:

{-147.83 mm, -304.30 mm, 1 371.70 mm, 0.174 rad, 1.964 rad, -1.949 rad}

The desired trajectory executed by the robot in this experiment can be observed in the Fig. 36.

Fig. 36. Experiment 2: Desired end-effector trajectory 2.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 37.

Fig. 37. Experiment 2: Joints position resulting of trajectory 2.

The graph of the flags arrives to 1 in the middle of the movement, which indicates the low manipulability flag, due to the closeness to a singularity.

The following Fig. 38 and Fig. 39 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 38. Experiment 2: Simulator results with trajectory 2.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 39. Experiment 2: Real robot results with trajectory 2.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

5.4.3. Experiment 3

This third experiment also uses the Trajectory 2 changing again the initial joints position:

{5, -74.19, -17.24, -73.56, 5, 5} degrees

and the initial end-effector pose, with Cardan orientation representation, is:

{-147.83 mm, -304.30 mm, 1 460.00 mm, 0.174 rad, 1.964 rad, -1.949 rad}

This initial end-effector pose is close to the end of the workspace. When the desired points of the trajectory are outside the robot workspace, the robot cannot reach the position. In this example, this is the reason why the results of applying CLIK to obtain the joints values from the desired trajectory (Fig. 40) are not valid. This can be observed at Fig. 41, when the end-effector tolerance violation error flag appears and the joints of the robot enter in an oscillatory behaviour. In the simulator, as can be observed at Fig. 42, the robot links fall erratically. Like the trajectory of the erratic movement of the real robot is not predictable, this experiment is not tested with the real robot. That is why this example is only executed in the simulator.

Fig. 40. Experiment 3: Desired end-effector trajectory 2.

Fig. 41. Experiment 3: Joints position resulting of trajectory 2.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 42. Experiment 3: Simulator results with trajectory 2.
 (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

5.4.4. Experiment 4

The desired trajectory (Fig. 43) followed in this experiment is the Trajectory 1, but instead of spending 21 seconds and going down 10 cm, the complete trajectory spends 121 seconds and moves the end-effector 80 cm from the initial position.

The initial joints position for this experiment is:

{5, -101.57, 40.41, -103.84, 5, 5} degrees

and the initial end-effector pose, with Cardan orientation representation, is:

{-148.06 mm, -304.32 mm, 1 400.00 mm, 0.174 rad, 1.964 rad, -1.949 rad}

Fig. 43. Experiment 4: Desired end-effector trajectory.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 44.

Fig. 44. Experiment 4: Joints position resulting of trajectory.

The following Fig. 45 and Fig. 46 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 45. Experiment 4: Simulator results with trajectory. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 46. Experiment 4: Real robot results with trajectory. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

5.4.5. Experiment 5

In this case, the desired trajectory (Fig. 47) to follow in 21 seconds is more complex, since it is a combination of the following trajectories:

- Negative linear movement of 10 cm in X axis
- Positive linear movement of 10 cm in Y axis
- Negative linear movement of 10 cm in Z axis
- Negative orientation movement of 90 degrees

The initial joints position for this experiment is:

{5, -125.00, 90.00, -130.00, 5, 5} degrees

and the initial end-effector pose, with Cardan orientation representation, is:

{-112.14 mm, -301.17 mm, 1 128.82 mm, 0.174 rad, 1.964 rad, -1.949 rad}

Fig. 47. Experiment 5: Desired end-effector trajectory.

The theoretically computed by CLIK joints position results are shown in the Fig. 48.

Fig. 48. Experiment 5: Joints position resulting of trajectory.

The following Fig. 49 and Fig. 50 show respectively the end-effector trajectory and the movement of the joints done in the simulator and with the real robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 49. Experiment 5: Simulator results with trajectory. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 50. Experiment 5: Real robot results with trajectory. (a) End-effector trajectory. (b) Movement of the joints.

5.5. Results

As can be seen in the figures of the Experiment 1, the Experiment 2, the Experiment 4 and the Experiment 5, with the success flag and the low manipulability warning flag, the end-effector position movement is correctly following the input desired end-effector trajectory.

This is not the case when the end-effector tolerance violation error flag appears, as in the Experiment 3. It is the user's responsibility to stop the robot when this flag appears to avoid erratic movements.

In the joints movement graphs of the real robot, the velocity appears noisy. This noise is assumed as normal since the control loop is doing control in velocity and not in position. The decision of doing velocity control instead of position control (that is the objective of the project) is taken to solve an inherent problem of the UR10e robot. This robot has a delay of 30 ms when is controlled with position that would create problems with our implementation. For this reason, the control is in velocity instead of position.

The robot needs a specific communication frequency (500 Hz for the UR10e), that is translated to a specific small duration of the iteration execution (2 ms for the UR10e). To check how much time of the 2 ms is being used in the calculation of the inverse kinematics, the CPU time used by the CLIK `getResults` function has been measured.

The durations depicted in Fig. 51 are from executing the Experiment 1 with the Trajectory 1 with the simulator in the TTL Tekno Pro PC. They can be considered as normal, since even the testing program is executed with the highest priority (as it is explained in section 5.3), it is not Real-Time.

Fig. 51. Durations of the iterations execution in the TTL Tekno Pro PC with the simulator.

Both graphs of Fig. 52 are executing the Experiment 1 with the trajectory, as it happens with Fig. 51. But in this case, the durations of the Fig. 52 should be constant because the testing program is executed in Real-Time mode with the real robot in the FCC PC. Nevertheless, as

it can be observed at Fig. 52 (a) the execution times are spread in groups of different durations. Fig. 52 (b) shows another example of more constant durations, but still with a lot of outliers execution times. In future tasks, this problem with the execution times should be investigated.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 52. Durations of the iterations execution in the FCC PC with the real robot.
(a) High difference. (b) More constant.

5.6. Legal, ethic and professional responsibility

This project contributes to the proper functioning of the FCC robotic system, which will be able to work autonomy and teleoperated.

One of its main objectives is avoiding the human direct interaction with radioactive areas like the FCC will be many times. This is promoting the welfare of human beings.

A use of the autonomy FCC robotic system will decrease machine down time, facilitating fast and robust interventions. Many of the manual or less automated interventions in the current LHC complex are not able to be easily applied to a three times longer FCC tunnel. It will suppose either increasing efforts in workforce and money or accepting longer machine down times.

In terms of this specific project, the behaviour of the program implemented is transparent because all the actions are directly consequence of the inputs, without intelligent systems interfering.

Furthermore, all the code is exposed to unit tests with two main objectives:

- avoiding the inappropriate use, since, before any change in the code, the execution of the unit tests will tell if there is any erroneous behaviour,
- protecting against the wrong working, because all the erratic functioning is contemplated and have error warning mechanisms.

Thanks to these characteristics, the programs developed in these projects are legally, ethically and professionally responsible.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This project achieves its main objective of solving the inverse kinematics problem, using the CLIK algorithm with the Jacobian, for carrying out the control in position of a redundant robot, with 11 degrees of freedom, avoiding singularities, as it is exposed in the Results.

Like it is explained in the chapter 4, all the written codes follow the CRF structure and are inserted without negatively impacting the other CRF already developed programs.

This project is successfully open to the addition of Objective Functions, which is the following step that is being carried through at CERN. This report is part of the documentation of the project.

As the experiments done in this project have been carried out with the UR10e robot, which is a different robot from the one that has been considered for its design, and the results are successful, it can be affirmed that the IK resolution implemented in this project is generic.

6.1. Future improvements

Even though all the objectives of this thesis were achieved, there are still aspects to improve.

- Executing time

As it is exposed in the Results, the execution times of CLIK program are inconsistent in the Real-Time system. There might be different reasons for this undesired behaviour.

The problem can be originated from the code itself, and in this case, the Real-Time characteristics need to be improved (for example, making sure that there are no unnecessary memory allocation, dynamic variables, or others). The easiest way to identify it is by creating a simple program to try to reproduce the problematic behaviour.

The program is executed with the maximum priority together with processes that cannot be stopped, like the watchdog of the PC. This means that the problem could be created by the scheduler if it stops or moves the threads between CPU cores, making use of the cache for upload and download.

- Thread-safe

For the moment CLIK program cannot be called by different threads and ensure proper results. In the future, this will be necessary, thus the program will need to be thread-safe.

- Change parser library

When the parser was chosen, the ExprTk was considered the best one. Nevertheless, a lot of problems came from it, during the implementation of the kinematic library (no matrix treatment, no possibility of copying, assigning, or comparing), but the most important one that concerns this project is the time it takes to evaluate the mathematical expressions. If better options appear in the market they should be tested.

- Objective Functions

The subsequent extension of the project will consist of adding Objective Functions to set some restrictions to the robot. Joint limits, collision avoidance, attracted joints position, singularity avoidance and static torque optimization could be possible implementations.

7. BUDGET

The content included in this budget encompass the cost of the developing, the implementation and the testing of this project carried out at CERN, which is a non-profit organization. For this reason, this budget shows the cost without taking care of industrial profit and taxes applied to the summarised amount.

7.1. Elementary prices table

7.1.1. Material cost

The TABLE X shows the prices per unit of all the materials needed for the project, both hardware (hm – hardware material) and software (sm – software material).

TABLE X
Material cost

Code	Unit	Description	Price (€)
hm1	% · unit	PC TTL Tekno Pro - Intel i7-3770	189.00
hm2	% · unit	Dell U2415 Monitor	154.99
hm3	% · unit	Logitech B100 Mouse	5.99
hm4	% · unit	Dell KB1421 Keyboard	25.34
sm1	unit	Ubuntu 20.04 Operating System	0.00
sm2	unit	Eigen Library	0.00
sm3	unit	ExprTk Library	0.00
sm4	unit	Nlohmann JSON Library	0.00
hm9	% · unit	UR10e Robot	30 000.00
hm10	% · unit	UR10e Controller	8 000.00
hm11	% · unit	Robot Base	100.00
hm12	% · unit	Power supply	800.00
hm13	% · unit	PC Compulab Fitlet2 - Intel Atom-E3950	399.00
sm5	unit	UR E-series SIM for Linux 5.9.4	0.00

The hardware materials used in this project are not bought just for this project. For this reason, the hardware materials have 2 units for measuring the quantity:

- the number of units (pieces), and
- the percentage of the time that are used, considering a depreciation of 5 years.

7.1.2. Labor cost

The TABLE XI shows the hourly payment of the personnel participating in the project.

TABLE XI
Labor cost

Code	Unit	Description	Price (€)
h1	h	Engineering graduate - Main developer	13.83
h2	h	Engineer - Project supervisor	15.50
h3	h	Engineer - Programming supervisor	17.32

7.1.3. Other direct costs

To include the cost of all the auxiliary means (tools and wiring, among others) used in the project, a percentage (TABLE XII) is added to the budget on the total direct costs.

TABLE XII
Other direct costs

Code	Unit	Description	Price (€)
	%	Other direct costs	2%

7.2. Decomposed prices table

The budget of this project has only one chapter with two items. The first item (I_1.1) that encompasses the development and the implementation is detailed at TABLE XIII, and the second item (I_1.2) that comprises testing with the real robot is shown at TABLE XIV.

TABLE XIII
I_1.1: Development and implementation

Code	Description	Price (€)	Quantity	Unit	Total (€)
hm1	PC TTL Tekno Pro - Intel i7-3770	189.00	14.23	1 % · unit	26.89
hm2	Dell U2415 Monitor	154.99	14.23	1 % · unit	22.06
hm3	Logitech B100 Mouse	5.99	14.23	1 % · unit	0.85
hm4	Dell KB1421 Keyboard	25.34	14.23	1 % · unit	3.61
sm1	Ubuntu 20.04 Operating System	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm2	Eigen Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm3	ExprTk Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm4	Nlohmann JSON Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
h1	Engineering graduate - Main developer	13.83	351.00	h	4 854.33
h2	Engineer - Project supervisor	15.50	191.00	h	2 960.50
h3	Engineer - Programming supervisor	17.32	191.00	h	3 308.12
	Other direct costs	11 176.36	2	%	223.53
Development and implementation total cost:					11 399.89

7. BUDGET

TABLE XIV
I_1.2: Testing

Code	Description	Price (€)	Quantity	Unit	Total (€)
hm2	Dell U2415 Monitor	154.99	3.46	2 % · unit	10.73
hm3	Logitech B100 Mouse	5.99	3.46	2 % · unit	0.41
hm4	Dell KB1421 Keyboard	25.34	3.46	2 % · unit	1.75
hm9	UR10e Robot	30 000.00	3.46	1 % · unit	1 038.00
hm10	UR10e Controller	8 000.00	3.46	1 % · unit	276.80
hm11	Robot Base	100.00	3.46	1 % · unit	3.46
hm12	Power supply	800.00	3.46	1 % · unit	27.68
hm13	PC Compulab Fitlet2 - Intel Atom-E3950	399.00	3.46	1 % · unit	13.81
sm1	Ubuntu 20.04 Operating System	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm2	Eigen Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm3	ExprTk Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm4	Nlohmann JSON Library	0.00	1	unit	0.00
sm5	UR E-series SIM for Linux 5.9.4	0.00	1	unit	0.00
h1	Engineering graduate - Main developer	13.83	30.00	h	414.90
h2	Engineer - Project supervisor	15.50	9.00	h	139.50
h3	Engineer - Programming supervisor	17.32	9.00	h	155.88
	Other direct costs	2 082.92	2.00	%	41.66
Testing total cost:					2 124.58

7.3. Unitary prices table

The following TABLE XV shows the unitary price of each item of the project.

TABLE XV
Unitary prices

Code	Unit	Description	Price (€)
I_1.1	unit	Development and implementation	11 399.89
I_1.2	unit	Testing	2 124.58

7.4. Valuation of the project

The TABLE XVI presents the calculation of the total material execution budget of this project.

TABLE XVI
Total material execution budget of chapter 1

Code	Description	Price (€)	Quantity	Unit	Total (€)
I_1.1	Development and implementation	11 399.89	1	unit	11 399.89
I_1.2	Testing	2 124.58	1	unit	2 124.58
Total material execution budget of chapter 1:					13 524.46

The addition of the execution budget of the all the chapters of the budget results in the total material execution budget. As can be seen at TABLE XVII, like this budget only has one chapter, the total material execution budget corresponds to the chapter 1.

TABLE XVII
Total material execution budget

Code	Description	Price (€)
1	Project	13 524.46
Total material execution budget:		13 524.46

7.5. Budget summary

TABLE XVIII shows the total cost of the project, which corresponds to the material execution budget plus the general and administrative expenses. But, as it is explained at the beginning of this chapter 7, this budget does not include industrial profit, neither taxes.

TABLE XVIII
Budget summary

Description	Price (€)
Total material execution budget	13 524.46
General and administrative expenses (13%)	1 758.18
Total cost of the project:	15 282.64

The total cost of the project is:

FIFTEEN THOUSAND TWO HUNDRED AND EIGHTY-TWO EUROS AND SIXTY-FOUR CENTS

8. PROJECT PLANNING

This project has been carried out in 37 weeks. As can be seen in TABLE XIX, starting on July 22nd of 2021 and finishing on June 22nd of 2022.

TABLE XIX
Gantt Diagram Summary

Code	Task	Start date	End date	Hours
1	Project definition	22/07/2021	06/08/2021	4
2	Study of the art	26/07/2021	27/07/2021	4
2.1	Inverse Kinematics	28/07/2021	06/08/2021	18
2.2	Inverse Kinematics Libraries	05/08/2021	06/08/2021	5
3	Define structure IK implementation	09/08/2021	13/08/2021	8
4	Implementation			
4.1	Jacobian	02/09/2021	29/09/2021	53
4.1.1	Parser	12/08/2021	08/12/2021	50
4.2	Forward Kinematics	23/09/2021	20/10/2021	45
4.3	Error Computation	02/12/2021	15/12/2021	15
4.4	CLIK	09/12/2021	30/03/2022	70
4.5	Code optimization	31/03/2022	14/04/2022	8
5	Tests	24/02/2022	09/03/2022	6
5.1	Simulations	03/03/2022	08/04/2022	27
5.2	Real robot	10/03/2022	18/05/2022	30
6	Results analysis	19/05/2022	26/05/2022	8
7	Project report	22/11/2021	22/06/2022	30
Total:		22/07/2021	22/06/2022	381

As is shown in the complete Gantt Diagram (ubicated in the Appendix) there are periods in which no work has been done on this project:

- From 21/10/2021 to 21/11/2021: working in another project
- From 20/12/2021 to 01/02/2022: vacations
- From 15/04/2022 to 01/05/2022: vacations

This project has been done during an internship at CERN, where also other tasks have been carried out.

The total amount of hours working on this project is 381 hours. A quantity only a bit higher than the required on the 12 ECTS credits that which corresponds to 300 - 360 hours (1 ECTS is equivalent to 25 - 30 hours).

During all the project, weekly meetings have been held on Thursdays. On these meetings the project team planned the specific work for the following week. For this the reason, as can be seen in the complete Gantt Diagram, most of the tasks starts and finishes around Thursdays.

9. ABBREVIATIONS, UNITS AND ACRONYMS

A

AST: Abstract Syntax Tree

B

BFGS: Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb and Shanno

C

CASCLIK: CasADI-Based Closed-Loop Inverse Kinematics

CCD: Cyclic Coordinate Descent

CERN: European Council for Nuclear Research

CLIK: Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics

cm: centimetre

CRF: CERN Robotic Framework

Ctor: Constructor

D

DLS: Damped Least Squares

DOF: Degrees Of Freedom

Dtor: Destructor

E

ECTS: European Credit Transfer System

ExprTk: Mathematical Expression Toolkit Library

€: Euro

F

FABRIK: Forward and backward reaching inverse kinematics

FCC: Future Circular Collider

FK: Forward Kinematics

G

GPA: Graphical Programming Environment

H

HL-LHC: High-Luminosity LHC

hm: hardware materials

HTM: Homogeneous Transformation Matrix

Hz: Hertz

I

IK: Inverse Kinematics

ISO: International Standard Organization

J

JSON: JavaScript Object Notation

K

KDL: Kinematic and Dynamic Library

km: kilometre

L

LHC: Large Hadron Collider

M

m: metre

MDFP: Master's Degree Final Project

mm: millimetre

ms: millisecond

O

OOP: Object Oriented Programming

Orocos: Open Robot Control Software

R

rad: radians

RIA: Robot Institute of America

RTDE: Real-Time Data Exchange

RUR: Rossum's Universal Robots

S

s: second

SDLS: Selectively Damped Least Squares

sm: software materials

SMCM: Sequential Monte Carlo methods

SVD: Singular Value Decomposition

T

TeV: Teraelectronvolt

U

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UPM: Polytechnic University of Madrid (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

UR: Universal Robots

10. GLOSSARY

B

Beams: Set of particles.

D

Differential kinematics: Relationship between the joint velocities and the corresponding end-effector linear and angular velocity.

H

Hadron: Proton–proton and heavy ion.

I

Inverse kinematics: Problem that consist in calculate the values that the joint coordinates of a robot have to adopt for getting that the end-effector of the robot was in a specific position and orientation.

J

JSON: It is a lightweight format for storing and transporting data.

P

Pose: Set of task end-effector position and task end-effector orientation.

R

Redundant robot: Robot with more degrees of freedom than the components in the task space.

S

Singularity: configuration in which the end-effector of the robot becomes blocked in certain directions.

T

Target position: desired position.

W

Workspace: the space in which the robot operates.

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APPENDIX 1

GANTT DIAGRAM

					July 2021																				
					Week 1							Week 2							Week 3						
					19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Code	Task	Start date	End date	Hours	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S
1	Project definition	22/07/2021	06/08/2021	4																					
2	Study of the art	26/07/2021	27/07/2021	4																					
2.1	Inverse Kinematics	28/07/2021	06/08/2021	18																					
2.2	Inverse Kinematics Libraries	05/08/2021	06/08/2021	5																					
3	Define structure IK implementation	09/08/2021	13/08/2021	8																					
4	Implementation																								
4.1	Jacobian	02/09/2021	29/09/2021	53																					
4.1.1	Parser	12/08/2021	08/12/2021	50																					
4.2	Forward Kinematics	23/09/2021	20/10/2021	45																					
4.3	Error Computation	02/12/2021	15/12/2021	15																					
4.4	CLIK	09/12/2021	30/03/2022	70																					
4.5	Code optimization	31/03/2022	14/04/2022	8																					
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5.1	Simulations	03/03/2022	08/04/2022	27																					
5.2	Real robot	10/03/2022	18/05/2022	30																					
6	Results analysis	19/05/2022	26/05/2022	8																					
7	Project report	22/11/2021	22/06/2022	30																					
Total:		22/07/2021	22/06/2022	381																					

APPENDIX 1 Gantt Diagram

Code	August 2021																												September 2021																		
	Week 4							Week 5							Week 6							Week 7					Week 8						Week 9														
	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19					
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